

WHO Guidelines for malaria

Systematic reviews, background papers and other unpublished evidence considered in the development of recommendations

Prevention/Preventive chemotherapies

Section

4.2.3 Seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC). In *WHO Guidelines for malaria*, 3 June 2022.

Title

Seasonal malaria chemoprevention for malaria in children in areas with seasonal malaria

Authors

Julie I Thwing, John Williamson, Irene Cavros, Achuyt Bhattarai, Julie Gutman

Contact

gmpfeedback@who.int

This report was reviewed by the Guideline Development Group on Malaria Chemoprevention, convened by the World Health Organization Global Malaria Programme to support the development of recommendations included in the *WHO Guidelines for malaria*. It is being made publicly available for transparency purposes and information, in accordance with the *WHO handbook for guideline development, 2nd edition (2014)*.

The designations employed and the presentation of the material in this publication do not imply the expression of any opinion whatsoever on the part of WHO concerning the legal status of any country, territory, city or area or of its authorities, or concerning the delimitation of its frontiers or boundaries. Dotted and dashed lines on maps represent approximate border lines for which there may not yet be full agreement.

The mention of specific companies or of certain manufacturers' products does not imply that they are endorsed or recommended by WHO in preference to others of a similar nature that are not mentioned. Errors and omissions excepted, the names of proprietary products are distinguished by initial capital letters.

All reasonable precautions have been taken by WHO to verify the information contained in this publication. However, the published material is being distributed without warranty of any kind, either expressed or implied. The responsibility for the interpretation and use of the material lies with the reader. In no event shall WHO be liable for damages arising from its use.

The named authors alone are responsible for the views expressed in this document.

The findings and conclusions in this paper are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.

Seasonal malaria chemoprevention for malaria in children in areas with seasonal malaria

Julie I Thwing, John Williamson, Irene Cavros, Achuyt Bhattarai, Julie Gutman¹

¹Centers for Disease Control and Prevention

Dates

Date of Search:	11/18/2020
Protocol First Published:	9/30/2020
Review First Published:	

Summary of evidence

Effect on malaria incidence: Seasonal malaria chemoprevention, regardless of transmission setting, age < 5 years or age 5-9 years, whether given in three to four cycles or five to six cycles, and regardless of drug regimen, reduced incidence of confirmed clinical malaria illness. Among studies that administered SMC to children < 10 years of age and reported incidence separately for children < 5 years and children 5-9 years, there was no difference in effect size between children < 5 years and children 5-9 years. (Grade: Moderate)

Effect on malaria prevalence: Seasonal malaria chemoprevention, regardless of transmission setting, age < 5 years or age 5-9 years, whether given in three to four cycles or five to six cycles, and regardless of drug regimen, reduced prevalence of malaria infection in end of season surveys. (Grade: Moderate)

Effect on prevalence of any anemia: Seasonal malaria chemoprevention, administered as SP+AQ, resulted in a small reduction in prevalence of any anemia (hemoglobin < 11mg/dL) in end of season surveys among both children < 5 years and children 5-9 years. Moderate effects were seen in the studies with the highest baseline parasite prevalence (>40%). (Grade: Moderate)

Effect on prevalence of moderate anemia (hemoglobin < 8 mg/dL): Seasonal malaria chemoprevention, administered as SP+AQ, resulted in a modest reduction in prevalence of moderate anemia in end of season surveys among children < 5 years in moderate to high transmission zones (baseline parasite prevalence > 10%). (Grade: Moderate)

Effect on incidence of severe malaria: Seasonal malaria chemoprevention, administered as SP+AQ in three to four cycles reduced incidence of severe malaria among both children < 5 years and children 5-9 years, in studies in which baseline parasite prevalence was > 2%. (Grade: High)

Effect on incidence of all cause hospitalization: Seasonal malaria chemoprevention reduced all-cause hospitalization in the two studies in which baseline parasite prevalence was $\geq 20\%$. (Grade: Moderate)

Effect on incidence of all-cause mortality: Seasonal malaria chemoprevention had no effect on all-cause mortality. (Grade: Low)

Effect on adverse events: Seasonal malaria chemoprevention has very low risk of serious or severe adverse events, < 1/100,000 cycles. Nausea, vomiting, and abdominal pain are more frequent in children who receive SMC than placebo. (Grade: High)

Expansion of age range to children 5-9 years: While primarily conducted in Senegal, studies including children < 10 years comparing effect size among children < 5 years with that in children 5-9 years found no difference in effect size for incidence, prevalence, any anemia, and severe malaria. All-cause hospitalization and all-cause mortality were not reported for children 5-9 years.

Increase in number of cycles: Studies in zones with a shorter transmission season generally used three to four cycles, while studies in zones with longer transmission seasons generally used five to six cycles, thus making direct comparison challenging, however, studies that used five to six cycles in zones with longer transmission seasons achieved comparable results to those seen with three to four cycles in zones with shorter transmission seasons.

Background

Malaria caused by *Plasmodium falciparum* remains a major cause of ill health and death in sub-Saharan Africa [1]. In the Sahel sub-region of Africa, most childhood malaria morbidity and mortality occurs during the rainy season, which lasts from 3-4 months [2, 3].

Since March 2012, the World Health Organization (WHO) has recommended seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) for children aged 3–59 months living in areas of highly seasonal malaria transmission in the Sahel subregion of Africa [4]. SMC is defined as the intermittent administration of full treatment courses of an antimalarial medicine (usually sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine + amodiaquine (SP+AQ)) to children in areas of highly seasonal transmission administered at monthly intervals, beginning at the start of the transmission season, to a maximum of four doses during the malaria transmission season.

The objective of SMC is to prevent malarial illness by maintaining therapeutic antimalarial drug concentrations in the blood throughout the period of peak seasonal malaria transmission. Systematic review and meta-analysis of SMC has shown that it offers young children a high level of protection against clinical malaria and all-cause mortality during malaria transmission season [5].

Since WHO's SMC policy recommendation in 2012, twelve countries in the Sahel subregion have scaled up SMC [1]. Of the 31 million children aged under 5 years in SMC-eligible areas, 62% received SMC in 2018. Since then, numerous studies have been published documenting the health benefits of SMC in a range of settings, regimens, and age-groups.

While the scale up in providing up to four cycles of SP+AQ to children 3-59 months has provided millions of children with chemoprevention during malaria transmission season, many National Malaria Control Programs are interested in increasing the number of rounds of treatment to cover a longer transmission season or extending the age range to 10 years as the malaria burden shifts to older children. In order to potentially "include additional at-risk groups and clarify contextual considerations for implementation" (WHO Chemoprevention GDG), a systematic review of the existing SMC evidence is needed.

Objectives

Main objective

To assess the effect of seasonal malaria chemoprevention with antimalarial drugs on malaria disease burden among children in zones of seasonal malaria transmission, stratified by age range of children (3-59 months vs 60-120 months), number of cycles (3-4 cycles vs 5-6 cycles), and drug regimen.

Secondary objective

To summarize contextual information for SMC regarding acceptability, feasibility, equity, safety, drug resistance, and cost effectiveness.

Methods

Criteria for considering studies for this review

Types of study included

For the main objective, the following study designs were included:

- Randomized designs
 - Cluster randomized controlled trials (RCTs) with at least two clusters per arm.

- Cluster-randomized stepped wedge designs with at least four clusters
- Individually randomized controlled trials
- Cluster-randomized cross over trials with: (a) at least two clusters per arm and (b) a suitable washout period during which the intervention is no longer applied
- Non-randomized designs
 - Controlled before-and-after studies (CBAs) with: (a) a contemporaneous control group, and (b) at least two sites per arm.
 - Interrupted time series (ITS) studies with: (a) a clearly defined point in time when the intervention occurred, and (b) at least two (if a contemporaneous control group is available) or three (if no control group is available) data points collected both before the first round of SMC and after the last round of SMC, measured at evenly spaced intervals (i.e., monthly). Baseline up to one year prior to intervention is required.

Types of study excluded

For the main objective, we excluded studies if we observed the following:

- The follow-up periods for the intervention and control periods were not identical.
- There were insufficient pre- or post-intervention data points for ITS
- If co-interventions were conducted as part of the SMC campaign (i.e., ITNs, deworming, vaccination) were thus not balanced across arms, these studies were presented separately.

SMC for contextual factors (secondary objective)

In addition to studies evaluating the efficacy or effectiveness of SMC in areas of seasonal transmission, we screened all papers from the search for studies which contributed additional information on acceptability, feasibility, costing and cost effectiveness, resistance, immunological response, adherence to treatment, and other factors. Such studies could be of qualitative or quantitative design. All studies included in the review were based on primary data.

Types of participants

Children living in malaria-endemic areas of seasonal transmission were included, whether the intervention was applied individually or to the entire population of eligible children. The analysis was stratified by two age groups (3-59 months, 60-120 months).

Types of interventions

Intervention arm

In this review, seasonal malaria chemoprevention is defined as administration of a full therapeutic course of antimalarial medicine (irrespective of the presence of symptoms or infection) to eligible children living in a defined geographical area (except those for whom the medicine is contraindicated), during malaria transmission season, at approximately the same time and at repeated intervals. The analysis was stratified by SMC drug regimen used and number of cycles over the course of the season (3-4 cycles, 5-6 cycles).

Comparator(s)/control arm

Standard of care is defined as adequate access to case management including parasitologic confirmation of diagnosis and effective treatment, without any other preventive treatment among the target age group. Studies that included other malaria co-interventions (e.g. ITNs, IRS, source reduction activities and environmental management, enhanced case management) and non-malaria co-interventions (e.g. MDA campaigns for other neglected tropical diseases and mass nutritional supplementation activities such as ivermectin or vitamin A distribution) will be included. Ideally, all other malaria and non-malaria co-interventions must be balanced in all arms. Where these interventions are part of the SMC campaign and hence not balanced, these results will be presented separately.

Types of outcome measures

Studies reported at least one primary or secondary outcome for inclusion in the primary review, while studies that did not include a primary or secondary outcome, but did include contextual factors were reviewed for data related to contextual factors.

Primary outcomes

The primary outcome is confirmed malaria illness incidence, defined as febrile illness with diagnostically confirmed parasitaemia. Due to the geographic specificity, this is almost exclusively *P. falciparum*.

Secondary outcomes

1. Parasitaemia prevalence, as determined by microscopy, malaria RDT, or polymerase chain reaction (PCR)
2. Parasitaemia incidence (as measured in a cohort)
3. Anemia prevalence (as measured through cross sectional survey)
4. Blood transfusions, defined as number of patients requiring blood transfusion
5. Hospital admissions (all-cause and malaria specific)
6. Severe malaria, defined as number of patients admitted with severe malaria
7. All-cause mortality
8. Known adverse effects related to SMC drugs using WHO definitions
9. Educational outcomes for school aged children (school attendance)

In the studies that met criteria for inclusion, no studies reported parasitemia incidence (#2) or blood transfusions (#4), and only one reported education outcomes. Studies that reported hospitalization reported all-cause, rather than malaria-specific hospitalizations.

Contextual factors

- **Safety:** Inadvertent treatment of those for whom the drug is contraindicated; overdose or aspiration in children
- **Drug resistance:** Increases prevalence of drug resistance markers for amodiaquine, sulfadoxine, and pyrimethamine
- **Immunological impacts:** changes in seroprevalence to a panel of malaria antigens
- **Operational and feasibility considerations:** improving compliance to target number of doses and adherence to individual treatment rounds; delay between doses; timing of doses; strategies for those ineligible to receive the medication
- **Equity:** impact of the intervention on health equity
- **Acceptance:** Population acceptability of SMC
- **Resource use:** Costing studies or cost-effectiveness evaluations

Timing of outcome assessment

The protocol envisioned baseline and follow up measures taking place at the same months of the year, with:

- cross sectional measures assessed during the same months for baseline and subsequent measurements;
- incidence data similarly including the same time periods for baseline and follow up, with preferably a full year for both baseline and follow up.

However, it was found that outcome measures were not assessed in this manner. Incidence measures (incidence, severe malaria, hospitalization, and death) were reported starting from the day of the first cycle to 4-6 weeks after the last cycle, while prevalence measures were generally a comparison between arms of an endline cross sectional survey conducted 4-6 weeks after the last cycle. In studies in which a baseline cross sectional survey was performed, the baseline was conducted a month or two before the first cycle of SMC.

Search methods for identification of studies

We attempted to identify all relevant studies regardless of language or publication status (published, unpublished, in press, ongoing). In addition to studies evaluating the efficacy or effectiveness of SMC, we screened all papers from the search for additional information on acceptability, feasibility, costing, drug resistance, adherence to treatment, and other factors. Such studies could be of qualitative or quantitative design. Only studies using empirical, primary data were included in this review.

Electronic searches

Studies were identified through comprehensive electronic database searches using study specific search terms (Annex 1). The following databases were included in the search: Cochrane Infectious Diseases Group Specialized Register; Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), published in The Cochrane Library; MEDLINE (PubMed); EMBASE (OVID); and LILACS. We also searched Global Health; ProQuest Natural Science Collection; ZETOC; Tropical Diseases Bulletin; The Archives of the World Health Organization; US National Institute of Health Ongoing Trials Register (www.ClinicalTrials.gov/); ISRCTN registry (www.isrctn.com/); The WHO's International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (WHO ICTRP) (www.who.int.ictrp).

Searching other resources

Reference lists

For articles prior to 2000, we searched the reference lists of previous reviews (Matangila 2015, Meremikwu 2005, 2012; Wilson 2011) for previously unidentified

studies. Studies excluded from earlier reviews were screened in case they warranted inclusion in this review, to allow for inclusion of broader age range, number of rounds, types of studies, and non-efficacy related information (e.g., acceptability, costing).

Conference proceedings

The following recent proceedings were reviewed for relevant abstracts: Seventh Multilateral Initiative on Malaria Pan-African Malaria Conference (Dakar, Senegal; April 2018), American Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene (ASTMH) 67th Annual Meeting (New Orleans, LA, USA; November 2018), ASTMH 68th Annual Meeting (National Harbor, MD, USA; November 2019), and ASTMH 69th Annual Meeting (meeting virtual).

Data collection and analysis

Selection of studies

Two reviewers independently screened titles and abstracts identified from literature searches based on the pre-determined inclusion criteria. Any potentially relevant articles identified by at least one reviewer were evaluated by the same two reviewers for full-text eligibility based on the pre-determined inclusion criteria. A third reviewer was consulted to resolve any disagreements by discussion or consensus. French language articles were reviewed by a fluent French speaker (JT) to determine eligibility. For references selected for inclusion, we collated different publications reporting on the same study. Full-text studies that did not meet eligibility criteria are listed with their reasons for exclusion in table 17. The result of the study selection process is provided in a Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) flow diagram.

Data extraction and management

Two reviewers independently extracted information from studies on an electronic data extraction form. Any discrepancies in information were resolved by discussion to reach consensus or by consultation with a third reviewer. We attempted to contact the original study author(s) to retrieve any missing data or for clarifications.

Among studies that administered SMC to children up to 10 years of age, where these were presented separately, we abstracted and presented results by children < 5 years and children 5-9 years.

The following information was extracted:

- **Study design:** type; method of randomization (if applicable) and participant selection; adjustment for clustering (for cluster-RCTs); sample size; method (if

possible) of blinding of participants and personnel with respect to each outcome of interest.

- **Participants:** study settings (country, time frame, timing of transmission/rainy season, parasite prevalence, concurrent intervention coverage) and population characteristics; age groups; participation rates; withdrawal and loss to follow-up where available.
- **Intervention:** Drug regimen and dose, placebo control, coverage, number and timing of doses, method of delivery (fixed point, door to door), effective coverage
- **Outcomes:** definition of outcome; diagnostic method or surveillance method; population in which outcome was measured; number of events; number of participants or unit time; time point at which outcome was assessed in relation to SMC rounds, statistical power; unit of analysis; incomplete outcomes or missing data.
- **Contextual factors:** information on contextual factors (as defined under “Types of outcome measures”) were extracted from studies and summarized, but these data were not included in meta-analyses

For dichotomous outcomes (prevalence), we extracted the number of events and number of participants in each study arm. For rate data (incidence and mortality), we extracted the number of events, the total person time at risk or population at risk in each study arm, and a measure of variance (standard error) where available, or rate ratio, where reported.

For cluster-RCTs we recorded the number of clusters randomized; number of clusters analysed; measure of effect (such as risk ratio [RR], odds ratio, rate ratio, or mean difference [MD]) with confidence intervals (CI) or standard deviations; number of participants; and the intra-cluster correlation coefficient (ICC) value, where reported. In addition, for non-randomized studies, we extracted adjusted measures of intervention effects that attempt to control for confounding including RRs and rate ratios, where reported.

There were no interrupted time series or cross over trials eligible for inclusion.

Assessment of risk of bias in included studies

Two members of the review team independently assessed the risk of bias for each study that meets eligibility criteria using a tool (described below) designed to assess such risk and generating an overall assessment reported as low, moderate, serious,

critical or unclear, and summary graphs to display results. As the risk of bias in the effect of an intervention may be different for different outcomes, a 'Risk of bias' assessment for each outcome was made. We resolved any discrepancies through discussion or by consulting a third member of the review team.

For each included individual RCT, the Revised Cochrane 'Risk of Bias' (RoB 2) tool [7] was used from the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions, and the Rob 2 CRT was used for cluster-randomized trials [8]. We assessed non-randomized controlled studies by using the Cochrane Risk of Bias In Non-randomized Studies - of Interventions (ROBINS-I) tool [9]. The ROBINS-I tool recommends only including non-randomized studies that are not classified as having critical risk of bias. While studies with a critical risk of bias may meet the inclusion criteria, the review for such studies may include a descriptive analysis and report their estimates of effect. Given the number of high-quality randomized trials available, we included only randomized (individually and cluster randomized) studies in the primary analysis, and presented the non-randomized trials separately in tables. Uncontrolled before-and-after studies were assigned a high overall risk of bias due to the inherent biases associated with the study design.

Strategy for data synthesis

Measures of treatment effect

Risk ratios were used to summarize dichotomous outcomes for studies with a control group, and rate ratios were used for count outcomes. Measures of effects were presented with corresponding 95% confidence intervals (CI). To calculate incidence (of confirmed malaria, severe malaria, all cause hospitalizations, and all-cause mortality), the denominator was the person-time of observation, calculated as the size of the study or observed population multiplied by the number of months of observation. When controlled before and after measures for prevalence (of parasitemia and anemia) were presented, we abstracted numerators and denominators for each arm before and after for each measure, and performed a difference in differences (DiD) analysis.

Unit of analysis issues

For cluster RCTs, measures of effect adjusted for clustering were used when possible. For studies with multiple intervention arms, treatment arms were be combined if appropriate, or participants in the control group split so that they were only included once in the meta-analysis.

Dealing with missing data

In both individually and cluster randomized trials, there was a certain degree of loss to follow up. Where there was greater than 10% loss to follow up, studies were downgraded in risk of bias accordingly. No data imputation was applied.

Assessment of heterogeneity

We assessed heterogeneity by examining forest plots for overlapping CIs. Statistical heterogeneity was examined using the I^2 statistic and classified according to the criteria below [10]:

- Moderate: I^2 between 30% and 60%
- Substantial: I^2 values between 50% and 90%
- Considerable: I^2 values between 75% and 100%

If there was either substantial heterogeneity (I^2 statistic value above 50%) or inconsistency in the direction of the effect with non-overlapping CIs, or both, then we did not perform a meta-analysis. Clinical and methodologic explanations for heterogeneity were considered through subgroup analyses.

Assessment of reporting biases

We planned to examine reporting using funnel plots for a meta-analysis of 10 or more studies, to be analyzed visually for asymmetry and using formal tests for funnel plot asymmetry, however, no meta-analysis included 10 or more studies.

Data synthesis

Data from randomized and non-randomized studies were presented separately. We also stratified first by age group (< 5 years vs \geq 5 years), then by drug regimen (SP+AQ vs AQ-AS vs SP+AS), then by number of monthly cycles (3-4 cycles vs 5-6 cycles). While randomized studies were included in meta-analyses when appropriate, non-randomized studies were presented separately in tables and were not included in a meta-analysis. Given the small numbers of studies included in each meta-analysis, we used a fixed effect meta-analysis. For each study, a risk ratio or prevalence ratio was calculated or abstracted, and $\log[RR]$ and standard error calculated and inverse variance weighting used in the meta-analysis.

We used a fixed-effect meta-analysis to combine data given the small number of trials available for a meta-analysis for each outcome.

Subgroup analysis

The potential effect modifiers specified below were collected, when available, for each included study: transmission intensity (incidence or prevalence), age, levels of existing drug resistance, choice of drug, cycles per year, months of rain, timing (in relation to season) of administration, coverage of vector control, and school enrolment (if applicable). We stratified outcomes by these potential effect modifiers if there were enough studies in each group. All eligible studies had rounds separated in time by approximately a month and were in locations in which *Plasmodium falciparum* was by far the dominant species.

Quality of evidence

Quality of evidence will be assessed using the Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluations (GRADE) [11] certainty ratings as follows:

Table 1. Quality of evidence Grades

Grade	Definition
High	We are very confident that the true effect lies close to that of the estimate of the effect.
Moderate	We are moderately confident in the effect estimate: The true effect is likely to be close to the estimate of the effect, but there is a possibility that it is substantially different
Low	Our confidence in the effect estimate is limited: The true effect may be substantially different from the estimate of the effect.
Very Low	We have very little confidence in the effect estimate: The true effect is likely to be substantially different from the estimate of effect

Results

Description of studies

Included and excluded studies are described in detail in the Characteristics of Studies tables. Characteristics of included studies are included as Table 2. Characteristics of included studies, randomized studies and Table 3. Characteristics of included studies, non-randomized studies. Characteristics of excluded studies are included as an annex.

Results of the search

A total of 1998 studies were identified from searching electronic databases, registers, and other sources: 1972 from database search from 2000 onwards (18 November 2020), and 40 additional unique studies from four previous reviews (Meremikwu 2005, Meremikwa 2012, Matangila 2015, Wilson 2011). After de-duplication, 1981 articles were screened against title and abstract eligibility and 250 articles from the database search and 23 articles from previous reviews were assessed for full text eligibility criteria, as presented in the PRISMA diagram in Figure 1.

Figure 1. PRISMA diagram

Excluded studies

A total of 1964 articles were excluded; 1708 articles were excluded during title and abstract screening, and 256 were excluded during full text screening for the following reasons: 22 not in a setting with seasonal malaria, four duplicates, 88 with no primary or secondary outcomes (72 of these with contextual factors), ten modelling, eight intervention had < 3 cycles of SMC, 11 intervention is SMC + nutritional

supplementation, five intervention is SMC + azithromycin, two intervention is given year-round (not seasonally), two intervention is IPTi (not SMC), 28 design is not controlled, ten have inappropriate control (case-control or unexposed in cross sectional survey), eight comparator is other regimens or operational strategies, seven are protocol only, three had no primary data, seven are reviews, fourteen cross reference with an included study, two had <2 areas/clusters per arm, and two are abstracts only (unable to contact author).

Table 2. Characteristics of included studies, randomized studies

Study	Country	Design	Age group	Comparison	# of cycles	Number enrolled	Coverage	Parasite prevalence	ITN use	Rains	Months given
Ambe 2020	Nigeria	cRCT	3-59 mo	SP+AQ vs placebo	4	204 SMC, 195 control (survey)	73% received all cycles	79%	>60%	June-Sept	Aug, Sept, Oct, Nov
Cisse 2006	Senegal	iRCT	2-59 mo	SP+AS vs placebo	3	542 SMC, 546 control	~95% per cycle	36-37%	< 25%	July-Sept	Sept, Oct, Nov
Cisse 2016	Senegal	stepped wedge	3-119 mo	SP+AQ vs nothing	3	2008: 14,000 2009: 90,000 2010: 160,000	2008: 93% 2009: 84% 2010: 93%	1-2%	50-80%	July-Sept	Sept, Oct, Nov
Dicko 2011	Mali	iRCT	3-59 mo	SP+AQ vs placebo	3	1509 SMC, 1508 placebo	>95% per cycle	13%	>90%	July-Oct	Aug, Sept, Oct
Konate 2011	Burkina Faso	iRCT	3-59 mo	SP+AQ vs placebo	3	1509 SMC, 1505 placebo	70-80% per cycle	42%	>90%	July - Oct	August, Sept, Oct
Kweku 2008	Ghana	iRCT	3-59 mo	AS-AQ vs placebo	6	626 SMC, 650 placebo	>95% per cycle	20%	<25%	April-July; Sept - Nov	May, June, July, Aug, Sept, Oct
Ndiaye 2019	Senegal	cRCT	3-119 mo	SP+AQ vs control	5	2245 SMC, 2301 control	> 90% per cycle	18% < 5 yr, 25% 5-9 yr	>90%	May-Oct	July, Aug, Sept, Oct, Nov
Sesay 2011	Gambia	iRCT	6-59 mo	SP+AQ vs placebo	3	639 SPAQ, 638 placebo	>95% per cycle	1%	>90%	July - Sept	Sept, Oct, Nov
Tagbor 2011	Ghana	cRCT	3-59 mo	AS-AQ vs control	3	800 SMC, 800 control	30% received all cycles	33%	NR	May-Nov	May, July, Sept
Tagbor 2016	Ghana	iRCT	3-59 mo	SP+AQ vs placebo	5	741 SMC, 749 control	36% received all cycles; ~70% per cycle	27%	>90%	May-Nov	July, Aug, Sept, Oct, Nov
Thera 2018	Mali	iRCT	6-15 mo	AS-AQ vs nothing	4	100 SMC, 100 control	Not reported	8-15%	NR	July-Oct	Oct, Nov, Dec, Jan
Tine 2014	Senegal	cRCT	3-119 mo	SP+AQ vs control	3	1000; 500 per arm	~90% per cycle	9%-11%	>90%	July-Oct	Sept, Oct, Nov

Table 3. Characteristics of included studies, non-randomized studies

Study	Country	Design	Age group	Comparison	# of cycles	Number enrolled	coverage	Parasite prevalence	ITN use	Rains	Months given
Issiaka 2020	Mali	Cross sectional survey	3-59 mo	SP+AQ vs nothing monthly	4	Survey: 2759 SMC, 3879 control	Not reported	50%	>80%	July-Oct	Aug, Sept, Oct, Nov
Opoku 2016	Ghana	Cluster controlled (2 clusters per arm)	6-15 years	AL+anti-parasitic vs anti-parasitic* every 3 months	3	AL+alb+praz: 90 alb+praz:127	Not reported	Not reported	40%	May-Nov	June, Sept, Dec
Salissou 2017	Niger	Cross sectional survey, 48 villages	3-59 mo	SP+AQ monthly vs nothing	4	Survey: 241 SMC, 241 control	Not reported	56%		July-Sept	
Wagman 2020	Mali	cluster controlled	3-59 mo	SP+AQ monthly + IRS vs IRS vs SP+AQ monthly vs nothing	4	Pop: IRS+SMC: 334,000; IRS: 236,000, SMC 394,000; control 1.42M	>90% (administrative coverage)	50%	>80%	July-Oct	Aug, Sept, Oct, Nov
Zongo 2015	Burkina Faso	individual controlled	3-59 mo	SP+AQ vs control, DP vs control, monthly	3	757 DP, 742 SP+AQ, 250 control	>95% per cycle	40-60%		July - Oct	Aug, Sept, Oct

*Both given every 3 months

Included studies

Twelve randomized and five non-randomized studies (seventeen total) met criteria for inclusion. (Characteristic of included studies tables, Tables 2 and 3)

Study design

We considered randomized controlled trials, whether the unit of randomization was the cluster (if at least two clusters per arm) or the individual. We also considered non-randomized designs if an appropriate control group was used (we did not consider case-controlled trials or cross-sectional surveys in which children in the population who did not receive SMC were considered controls as appropriate controls), as long as there were at least two clusters per arm in cluster-controlled trials.

Of the randomized designs, five were cluster randomized trials (Ambe 2020, Cisse 2016, Ndiaye 2019, Tagbor 2011, and Tine 2014), seven were individually randomized trials (Cisse 2006, Dicko 2011, Konate 2011, Kweku 2008, Sesay 2011, Tagbor 2016, and Thera 2018) and one was a randomized stepped wedge trial (Cisse 2016).

Study location

Four studies were in Senegal (Cisse 2006, Cisse 2016, Ndiaye 2016, Tine 2014), three studies were in Ghana (Kweku 2008, Tagbor 2011, Tagbor 2016), two studies were in Mali (Dicko 2011, Thera 2018), and one study each was in Burkina Faso (Konate 2011), Gambia (Sesay 2011), and Nigeria (Ambe 2020).

Study participants and interventions

Eight studies used sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine+amodiaquine (SP+AQ), four of which used three to four cycles in children < 5 years (Ambe 2020, Dicko 2011, Konate 2011, Sesay 2011), one of which used five cycles among children < 5 years (Tagbor 2016), two of which used three cycles in children < 10 years (Cisse 2016, Tine 2014) and one of which used five cycles in children < 10 years (Ndiaye 2019).

Three studies used artesunate-amodiaquine (AS-AQ), one used three cycles in children < 5 years, the one trial in which cycles were separated by 2 months (Tagbor 2011), one used six cycles in children < 5 years (Kweku 2008), and one used four cycles among school children 6-15 years (Thera 2018).

One study used sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine + artesunate (SP+AS), for three cycles, in children < 5 years (Cisse 2006).

Trials administering three to four cycles were usually located in the sites in the Sudano-sahelian bioclimatic region (Figure 2), with shorter transmission seasons, while studies administering five to six cycles were in or bordering the Guinean region, with longer transmission seasons.

Figure 2. Map of bioclimatic regions in west Africa

<https://eros.usgs.gov/westafrica/node/147>

Of the five non-randomized designs, one was an individual non-randomized controlled trial, which compared SP+AQ and dihydroartemisinin-piperazine (DP) in a randomized fashion, but did not include a randomized control group (Zongo 2015, Burkina Faso). Four were cluster non-randomized controlled: one used artemether-lumefantrine (AL) in three cycles among school children with anti-parasitics (albendazole+praziquantel) in both arms (Opoku 2016, Ghana), two compared four cycles of SP+AQ vs nothing among children <5 years (Issiaka 2020 in Mali and Salissou 2017 in Niger), and one compared IRS+SMC vs IRS vs SMC vs nothing in Mali, in which SMC was given as four cycles of SP+AQ to children < 5 years (Wagman 2020). For Zongo 2015, we presented the DP vs control and SP+AQ vs control separately, and for Wagman 2020, we presented SMC+IRS vs IRS and SMC vs nothing separately.

In the context of programmatic scale-up, case-controlled studies were conducted in numerous countries (ACCESS-SMC Partnership 2020), which while not considered a controlled design, were considered for contextual factors and were presented separately.

Outcomes

We looked at effects of SMC on incidence of confirmed malaria during the transmission season in which the SMC was administered, measured from the first cycle to four to six weeks after the end of the last cycle in most studies (episodes per person time at risk). Incidence of severe malaria, all-cause hospitalization, and all-cause mortality were also

measured in this fashion. Prevalence of malaria infection and anemia were measured in cross sectional surveys conducted at the end of the transmission season.

Table 4: Outcomes presented by study – randomized designs

Study	Country	design	Age group	# of cycles	Comparison	Outcomes
Ambe 2020	Nigeria	cRCT	3-59 months	4	SP+AQ vs control	prevalence, anemia
Cisse 2006	Senegal	iRCT	2-59 months	3	SP+AS vs placebo	incidence, severe malaria, mortality, prevalence
Cisse 2016	Senegal	randomized stepped wedge	3-119 months	3	SP+AQ vs control	incidence, severe malaria, mortality, prevalence, anemia
Dicko 2011	Mali	iRCT	3-59 months	3	SP+AQ vs placebo	incidence, severe malaria, hospitalization, mortality, anemia
Konate 2011	Burkina Faso	iRCT	3-59 months	3	SP+AQ vs placebo	incidence, severe malaria, hospitalization, mortality, prevalence, anemia
Kweku 2008	Ghana	iRCT	3-59 months	6	AS-AQ vs placebo	Incidence, hospitalization, mortality, prevalence
Ndiaye 2019	Senegal	cRCT	3-119 months	5	SP+AQ vs control	incidence, mortality, prevalence, anemia
Sesay 2011	Gambia	iRCT	6-59 months	3	SP+AQ vs placebo	incidence, hospitalization, mortality, prevalence, anemia
Tagbor 2011	Ghana	cRCT	3-59 months	3	AS-AQ vs control	prevalence, anemia
Tagbor 2016	Ghana	iRCT	3-59 months	5	SP+AQ vs placebo	incidence, prevalence, anemia
Thera 2018	Mali	iRCT	6-15 years	4	AS-AQ vs nothing	incidence
Tine 2014	Senegal	cRCT	3-119 months	3	SP+AQ vs control	incidence

Table 5: Outcomes presented by study – non-randomized designs

Study	Country	design	Age group	# of cycles	Comparison	Outcomes
Issiaka 2020	Mali	cluster non-randomized controlled	3-59 months	4	SP+AQ vs nothing	hospitalization, severe malaria, mortality
Opoku 2016	Ghana	cluster non-randomized controlled	6-15 years	3	AL+anti-parasitic vs anti-parasitic	prevalence, anemia
Salissou 2017	Niger	cluster non-randomized controlled	3-59 months	4	SP+AQ vs nothing	incidence, severe malaria, hospitalization, mortality, prevalence, anemia
Wagman 2020	Mali	cluster non-randomized controlled	3-59 months	4	SP+AQ + IRS vs IRS vs SP+AQ vs nothing	incidence
Zongo 2015	Burkina Faso	individual non-randomized control	3-59 months	3	SP+AQ vs control, DP vs control	incidence, mortality, prevalence, anemia

Contextual factors

Assessments for risk of bias for each study are summarized by outcome in Figure 3 and Figure 5, and for each study overall in Figures 4 and 6.

Risk of bias in included studies

Randomized studies

Randomized studies were assessed with the ROB2 tool from Cochrane using the following domains:

- **Domain 1a. Risk of bias arising from randomization:** All the individually randomized trials were low risk of bias. The cluster RCTs except Ambe 2020 and Tagbor 2011 were low risk of bias. Ambe 2020 was rated unclear as the randomization process for clusters was not described and the geographic distribution of intervention and control clusters suggested a lack of randomness; Tagbor 2011 also did not describe the process of randomization.
- **Domain 1b. Risk of bias from timing of identification/ recruitment:** Tagbor 2011 and Tine 2014 were rated unclear risk of bias. In both Tagbor 2011 and Tine 2014, children were enrolled after the randomization.
- **Domain 2. Risk of bias due to deviations from intended intervention:** Ambe 2020 and Tagbor 2011 were cluster randomized trials and were not placebo-controlled. Tagbor 2011 had low coverage and high and unbalanced loss to follow up, suggesting deviations from the intervention and likely unbalanced follow up. Ambe 2020 participants for the cross-sectional survey were selected after the

intervention had been implemented in an environment in which the intervention status was known. Thera 2018 was individually randomized but not placebo-controlled, and study staff, who measured outcome, were aware of the study group, without description of how this was addressed.

- **Domain 3. Missing outcome data:**

- **Incidence:** Except for Cisse 2016, the randomized designs were low risk. Cisse 2016 was assessed as unclear risk as it depended on surveillance of incidence by the health system, with personnel aware of the arm to which the cluster was assigned, and the proportion of infections confirmed parasitologically and the number of community health workers increased dramatically over the time of the study.
- **Severe malaria:** Except for Cisse 2016, all the randomized designs were low risk. Severe malaria was affected by the same factors as incidence, and it was rated as unclear risk.
- **Hospitalization:** All randomized designs were rated low risk.
- **Mortality:** The individually randomized controlled trials were rated low risk. Cisse 2016 was rated unclear risk for the same reason as incidence and severe malaria. Ndiaye 2019 used mortality reporters in both arms that found 12 deaths in the control arm and eight deaths in the SMC arm, but identified an additional six deaths when these children were absent for the SMC dose and were found to have died (undetected by the monitors). This strategy was not conducted in the control arm.
- **Prevalence:** All studies were rated low risk except for Tagbor 2011, which had a large and unbalanced loss to follow up in the end of season survey that measured malaria prevalence and was rated high risk.
- **Anemia prevalence:** All studies were rated low risk except for Tagbor 2011, which had a large and unbalanced loss to follow up in the end of season survey that measured anemia prevalence and was rated high risk.

- **Domain 4. Risk of bias in measurement of the outcome:**

- **Incidence:** The individually randomized, placebo-controlled trials were low risk. The cluster RCTs (Cisse 2016, Thera 2018, Tine 2014) were assessed as unclear risk as it depended on surveillance of incidence by the health system, by health care workers who were aware of the arm of the cluster. Thera 2018, which was individually randomized, but not placebo controlled, with personnel responsible for identifying symptomatic children aware of the study arm and relatively small enrollment, was rated at high risk of bias for incidence.
- **Severe malaria:** The individually randomized, placebo-controlled designs were all rated low risk. For Cisse 2016 and Tine 2014, both non-placebo-

- controlled cluster RCTs, severe malaria was affected by the same factors as incidence, and it was rated as unclear risk.
- **Hospitalization:** All studies reporting this outcome were individually randomized, placebo-controlled designs and were rated low risk.
 - **Mortality:** The individually randomized controlled trials were rated low risk. Cisse 2016 was rated unclear risk for the same reason as incidence and severe malaria. Ndiaye 2019 used mortality reporters in both arms that found 12 deaths in the control arm and eight deaths in the SMC arm, but identified an additional six deaths when these children were absent for the SMC dose and were found to have died (undetected by the monitors).
 - **Prevalence:** All studies were rated low risk.
 - **Anemia prevalence:** All studies were rated low risk.
- **Domain 5. Risk of bias in selection of reported result:** All randomized studies were rated low risk.

Non-randomized studies

Non-randomized studies were assessed with the following domains:

- **Domain 1. Failure to develop and apply appropriate eligibility criteria:** Issiaka 2020, Opoku 2016, Wagman 2020, and Zongo 2015 were rated unclear risk of bias given the uncontrolled choice of control populations, while Salissou was rated high risk due to lack of information on the control cluster selection.
- **Domain 2. Flawed measurement of exposure:** Opoku 2016 and Zongo 2015 both administered SMC to specific children and monitored them individually and were rated low risk. Issiaka 2020, Salissou 2017, and Wagman 2020 conducted cross sectional surveys or collected routine data in geographic areas where SMC was and was not administered, and were rated unclear.
- **Domain 3. Incomplete follow-up:**
 - **Incidence:** Zongo 2015 measured incidence by follow up of individual children and was rated low risk, Wagman 2020 measured through the routine surveillance system and was rated unclear risk, and Salissou 2017 measured by maternal report in a cross-sectional survey and was rated high risk.
 - **Severe malaria:** Issiaka 2020 and Salissou 2017 measured by maternal report in a cross-sectional survey and were rated high risk.
 - **Hospitalization:** Issiaka 2020 and Salissou 2017 measured by maternal report in a cross-sectional survey and were rated high risk.
 - **Mortality:** Issiaka 2020 and Salissou 2017 measured by maternal report in cross sectional surveys and were rated high risk. Zongo 2015 measured mortality by individual monitoring and was rated low risk.
 - **Prevalence:** Opoku 2016 and Zongo 2015 measured prevalence by follow up of individual children and were rated low risk. Salissou 2017 measured by cross sectional survey in which methodology was sparsely described, and was rated unclear risk.

- **Anemia prevalence:** Opoku 2016 and Zongo 2015 measured anemia prevalence by follow up of individual children and were rated low risk. Salissou 2017 measured by cross sectional survey and was rated unclear risk.
- **Domain 4. Flawed measurement of outcome:**
 - **Incidence:** Wagman 2020 measured through the routine surveillance system and was rated low risk, Zongo 2015 measured followed incidence in a control cohort which was enrolled a month after the study started and was rated unclear risk, and Salissou 2017 measured by maternal report in a cross-sectional survey (unconfirmed) and was rated high risk.
 - **Severe malaria:** Issiaka 2020 and Salissou 2017 measured by maternal report in a cross-sectional survey (unconfirmed) and were rated high risk.
 - **Hospitalization:** Issiaka 2020 and Salissou 2017 measured by maternal report in a cross-sectional survey (unconfirmed) and were rated high risk.
 - **Mortality:** Issiaka 2020 and Salissou 2017 measured by maternal report in cross sectional surveys (unconfirmed) and were rated high risk. Zongo 2015 measured mortality in a control cohort which was enrolled a month after the study started and was rated unclear risk.
 - **Prevalence:** Opoku 2016 and Salissou 2017 gave very sparse information as to the collection and analysis of prevalence data and were rated high risk.
 - **Anemia prevalence:** Opoku 2016 and Salissou 2017 gave very sparse information as to the collection and analysis of anemia prevalence data and were rated high risk.
- **Domain 5. Failure to adequately control for confounding:** Opoku 2016 and Salissou 2017 were rated high risk for high risk of confounding and no effort to control for it. Zongo 2015 was rated unclear risk for insufficient information as to analysis of the control population.

	Domain 1a	Domain 1b	Domain 2	Domain 3: Incidence	Domain 3: Severe malaria	Domain 3: Hospitalization	Domain 3: Mortality	Domain 3: Prevalence	Domain 3: Anemia	Domain 4: Incidence	Domain 4: Severe Malaria	Domain 4: Hospitalization	Domain 4: Mortality	Domain 4: Prevalence	Domain 4: Anemia	Domain 5	Overall: Incidence	Overall: Severe Malaria	Overall: Hospitalization	Overall: Mortality	Overall: Prevalence	Overall: Anemia
Ambe 2020	?	+	?					+	+					+	+	+					?	?
Cisse 2006	+		+	+	+		+	+		+	+		+	+		+	+	+		+	+	
Cisse 2016	+	+	+	?	?		?	+	+	?	?		?	+	+	+	?	?		?	+	+
Dicko 2011	+		+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Konate 2011	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Kweku 2008	+		+	+		+	+	+	+		+	+	+	+	+	+	+		+	+	+	+
Ndiaye 2019	+	+	+	+			+	+	+	?			+	+	+	+	?			+	+	+
Sesay 2011	+		+	+		+	+	+	+	+		+	+	+	+	+	+		+	+	+	+
Tagbor 2011	?	?	?					+	+					+	+	+					+	+
Tagbor 2016	+		+	+				+	+	+				+	+	+	+				+	+
Thera 2018	+		?	+						+						+	+					
Tine 2014	+	?	+	+	+					?	?					+	?	?				

Randomized studies: ROB2 tool: Domain 1a. Risk of bias arising from randomization; Domain 1b. Risk of bias from timing of identification/ recruitment; Domain 2. Risk of bias due to deviations from intended intervention; Domain 3. Missing outcome data; Domain 4. Risk of bias in measurement of the outcome; Domain 5. Risk of bias in selection of reported result.

Figure 1. Risk of bias summary: review authors' judgements about each risk of bias item for each included study by malaria outcomes, randomized studies

Randomized studies: ROB2 tool: Domain 1a. Risk of bias arising from randomization; Domain 1b. Risk of bias from timing of identification/ recruitment; Domain 2. Risk of bias due to deviations from intended intervention; Domain 3. Missing outcome data; Domain 4. Risk of bias in measurement of the outcome; Domain 5. Risk of bias in selection of reported result.

Figure 4: Risk of bias graph: review authors' judgements about each risk of bias item presented as percentages across all included studies, randomized studies

	Domain 1a	Domain 2	Domain 3: Incidence	Domain 3: Severe malaria	Domain 3: Hospitalization	Domain 3: Mortality	Domain 3: Prevalence	Domain 3: Anemia	Domain 4: Incidence	Domain 4: Severe Malaria	Domain 4: Hospitalization	Domain 4: Mortality	Domain 4: Prevalence	Domain 4: Anemia	Domain 5	Overall: Incidence	Overall: Severe Malaria	Overall: Hospitalization	Overall: Mortality	Overall: Prevalence	Overall: Anemia
Issiaka 2020	?	?		-	-	-				-	-	-			?		-	-	-		
Opoku 2016	?	+					+	+					-	-	+					-	-
Salissou 2017	-	?	-	-	-	-	?	?	-	-	-	-	-	-	?	-	-	-	-	-	-
Wagman 2020	?	?	?						+						?	?					
Zongo 2015	?	+	+			+	+	+	?			?	+	+	+	?			?	?	?

Non-randomized studies: Domain 1. Failure to develop and apply appropriate eligibility criteria (inclusion of control population); Domain 1b. Not applicable; Domain 2. Flawed measurement of exposure; Domain 3. Incomplete follow-up; Domain 4. Flawed measurement of outcome (outcome-level); Domain 5. Failure to adequately control for confounding (NOTE: Comer provided data on parasitemia during MDA, and thus contributed to AE outcomes only)

Figure 5. Risk of bias summary: review authors' judgements about each risk of bias item for each included study by malaria outcomes, non-randomized studies

Non-randomized studies: Domain 1. Failure to develop and apply appropriate eligibility criteria (inclusion of control population); Domain 1b. Not applicable; Domain 2. Flawed measurement of exposure; Domain 3. Incomplete follow-up; Domain 4. Flawed measurement of outcome (outcome-level); Domain 5. Failure to adequately control for confounding (NOTE: Comer provided data on parasitemia during MDA, and thus contributed to AE outcomes only)

Figure 6: Risk of bias graph: review authors' judgements about each risk of bias item presented as percentages across all included studies, non-randomized studies

Effects of interventions

Incidence of confirmed malaria (febrile illness + parasitemia of any density)

Incidence among children < 5 years during the transmission season in which SMC was administered

Four randomized studies demonstrated an effect on incidence of confirmed, symptomatic malaria with parasitemia of any density among children < 5 years, given 3-4 monthly cycles of SP+AQ. There was considerable heterogeneity among these studies in a range of transmission strata (Cisse 2016 Senegal, Dicko 2011 Mali, Konate 2011 Burkina Faso, and Sesay 2011 Gambia). One study of children < 5 years of children given three cycles of SP+AS (Cisse 2006 Senegal), two studies of children < 5 years given 5-6 rounds of SP+AQ (Ndiaye 2019 Senegal, Tagbor 2016 Ghana), and one study of children < 5 years given six cycles of AS-AQ (Kweku 2008 Ghana) also showed effect. There was no consistent impact of transmission intensity; among children who received 3-4 cycles of SP+AQ, the risk ratio was lower where transmission was higher (Senegal and Gambia vs Mali and Burkina Faso), but among children who received 5-6 cycles of SP+AQ, the risk ratio was higher where transmission was higher (Ghana vs Senegal). However, every study demonstrated substantial reduction of malaria incidence of SMC given to children < 5 years of age, regardless of drug regimen or number of cycles.

The evidence suggests that SMC given to children < 5 years of age results in a large reduction of malaria incidence during the transmission season in which SMC is given. (GRADE: Moderate)

Figure 7. Incidence among children < 5 years, by drug regimen, 3-4 cycles vs 5-6 cycles, randomized studies

Incidence in non-randomized studies

Three studies with non-randomized controls, two of which had multiple controls, reported effect on incidence, all among children < 5 years receiving three to four cycles. Zongo 2015 compared SP+AQ to DP in a randomized fashion, but the control group was not randomized. SP+AQ and DP had an effect that was comparable within the trial, and with randomized studies among children < 5 years receiving three to four cycles.

Table 6. Incidence among children < 5 years, by drug regimen, 3-4 cycles vs 5-6 cycles, non-randomized studies

Study IDs	Country	Comparator	Age group	# of cycles	N	Risk ratio
Salissou 2017	Niger	SP+AQ vs nothing	3-59 mo	4	241 SMC, 241 control	PR: 0.25 (0.20-0.31)
Wagman 2020A	Mali	SP+AQ + IRS vs IRS	3-59 mo	4	IRS+SMC: 334,000; IRS: 236,000,	RR: 0.96 (95% CI 0.51-1.37)
Wagman 2020B	Mali	SP+AQ vs nothing	3-59 mo	4	SMC 394,000; control 1.42M	RR: 0.84 (95% CI 0.45-1.55)
Zongo 2015A	Burkina Faso	SP+AQ vs nothing	3-59 mo	3	742 SP+AQ, 250 control	RR : 0.20 (95% CI 0.14-0.28)
Zongo 2015B	Burkina Faso	DP vs nothing	3-59 mo	3	757 DP, 250 control	RR: 0.26 (95% CI 0.19-0.35)

Incidence among children ≥ 5 years

Three studies reported results for malaria incidence among children ≥ 5 years, one for three cycles with SP+AQ in 5-9 years (Cisse 2016), one for four cycles of AS-AQ in school children 6-15 years (Thera 2018), and one for five cycles of SP+AQ in 5-9 years (Ndiaye 2019). While there was considerable heterogeneity, all showed substantial reduction in malaria incidence with SMC given to children ≥ 5 years of age, regardless of drug regimen or number of cycles.

The evidence suggests that SMC given to children ≥ 5 years of age results in a large reduction of malaria incidence during the transmission season in which SMC is given. (GRADE: Moderate)

Figure 8. Incidence among children ≥ 5 years, by drug regimen, 3-4 cycles vs 5-6 cycles, randomized studies

Incidence among children < 10 years, 3-4 cycles vs 5-6 cycles

Three studies reported incidence of malaria among children < 10 years, Cisse 2016 (also reported in results for < 5 and ≥ 5 years), Tine 2014 (only reported for children < 10 years), and Ndiaye 2019 (also reported in results for < 5 and ≥ 5 years), all in Senegal. Two (Cisse 2016 and Tine 2014) used three cycles while one (Ndiaye 2019) used five cycles. In this comparison, the evidence suggests a greater reduction in malaria incidence with five to six cycles compared to three to four cycles, however it should be noted that malaria transmission is substantially higher in the study site for Ndiaye 2019 than for Cisse 2016.

Figure 9. Incidence among children < 10 years, 3-4 cycles vs 5-6 cycles, randomized studies

Incidence in studies including children up to 10 years, comparing < 5 years to 5-9 years

Two studies administered SMC to children up to 120 months and reported malaria incidence for children < 5 years and 5-9 years separately. Cisse 2016 used three cycles of SP+AQ, while Ndiaye 2019 used five cycles of SP+AQ. (Cisse 2016 and Ndiaye 2019 report children < 5 years, while Cisse b and Ndiaye 2019B report children 5-9 years.) While the reduction in malaria incidence was greater with five cycles than with three as noted, there was no difference between effect size among children < 5 years or children 5-9 years, with either three or five cycles. The evidence suggests that a large and similar reduction in malaria incidence among children < 5 years and children 5-9 years who receive SMC.

*Cisse 2016 and Ndiaye 2019 report children < 5 years, while Cisse b and Ndiaye 2019B report children 5-9 years.

Figure 10. Incidence among children < 10 years, < 5 years vs 5-9 years, randomized studies

Prevalence of malaria infection at end of transmission season

Prevalence among children < 5 years

Four randomized studies demonstrated an effect on incidence of confirmed, symptomatic malaria with parasitemia of any density among children < 5 years, given 3-4 monthly cycles of SP+AQ with minimal heterogeneity, regardless of transmission strata (Ambe 2020 Nigeria, Cisse 2016 Senegal, Konate 2011 Burkina Faso, and Sesay 2011 Gambia).

One study of children < 5 years of children given three cycles of AS-AQ (Tagbor 2011 Ghana), one study of children < 5 years of children given three cycles of SP+AS (Cisse 2006 Senegal), two studies of children < 5 years given 5-6 rounds of SP+AQ (Ndiaye 2019 Senegal, Tagbor 2016 Ghana), and one study of children < 5 years given six cycles of AS-AQ (Kweku 2008 Ghana) also showed effect. While there was considerable heterogeneity, there was no consistent effect of number of cycles, drug regimen, or transmission intensity.

The evidence suggests a large reduction in malaria prevalence among children < 5 years who receive SMC. (GRADE: Moderate)

Figure 11. Prevalence among children < 5 years, by drug regimen, 3-4 cycles vs 5-6 cycles, randomized studies

Prevalence among children < 5 years in non-randomized designs

Three studies reported prevalence among children < 5 years, one that compared SP+AQ to DP (Zongo 2015), one that compared AL + anti-parasitics vs anti-parasitics (Opoku 2016), and one that compared SP+AQ to nothing (Salissou 2017)

Table 7. Prevalence among children < 5 years, non-randomized studies

Study ID	Country	Comparator	Age group	# of cycles	N	Prevalence ratio
Opoku 2016	Ghana	AL alb+praz vs alb+praz	6-15 years	3	AL+alb+praz: 90 alb+praz:127	PR: 0.46 (95% CI 0.21-0.98)
Salissou 2017	Niger	SP+AQ vs nothing	3-59 mo	4	241 SMC, 241 control	PR: 0.76 (95% CI 0.57-1.02)
Zongo 2015A	Burkina Faso	SP+AQ vs nothing	3-59 mo	3	742 SP+AQ, 250 control	PR: 0.42 (95% CI 0.31-0.55)
Zongo 2015B	Burkina Faso	DP vs nothing	3-59 mo	3	757 DP, 250 control	PR: 0.49 (95% CI 0.37-0.65)

Prevalence among children 5-9 years

One study, Ndiaye 2019, reported prevalence reduction separately among children 5-9 years.

Figure 12. Prevalence among children 5-9 years, randomized studies

Prevalence among children < 10 years

Two studies reported prevalence among all children under 10 years. While Cisse 2016, a randomized stepped wedge trial that administered three cycles of SP+AQ and collected data 2008-2010, reported malaria prevalence among children < 5 years in 2008, prevalence was reported for children < 10 years for 2009 and 2010 separately. Ndiaye 2019 administered five cycles of SP+AQ to children < 10 (results also presented in < 5 year and 5-9 year figures).

While there was substantial heterogeneity, overall, the evidence suggests a large reduction in malaria prevalence among children < 10 years who receive SMC. (GRADE: High)

Figure 13. Prevalence among children < 10 years, 3-4 cycles vs 5-6 cycles, randomized studies

Prevalence of anemia at end of transmission season

Prevalence of anemia was measured by cross sectional survey (or in individually randomized controlled trials, at end of season blood draw).

Prevalence of any anemia (hemoglobin < 11 mg/dL)

Prevalence of any anemia among children < 5 years

Six studies reported prevalence of any anemia (Hgb < 11 mg/dL) among children < 5 years. Three studies administered three to four cycles of SP+AQ (Ambe 2020, Dicko 2011, and Konate 2011) had substantial heterogeneity, but demonstrated a moderate effect. One study administered three cycles of AS-AQ (Tagbor 2011) and did not demonstrate an effect. Two studies administered five to six cycles of SP+AQ (Ndiaye 2019, Tagbor 2016), with small but consistent effect. The largest effect was seen in the two studies with the highest base line parasite prevalence (Ambe 2020 – 79%, Konate 2011 – 42%). The evidence suggests a modest effect of SMC on any anemia among children < 5 years. (Grade: Moderate)

Figure 14. Prevalence of any anemia among children < 5 years, by drug regimen, 3-4 cycles vs 5-6 cycles, randomized studies

Prevalence of any anemia among children < 5 years in non-randomized studies

Two studies reported any anemia: Opoku 2016 compared AL + albendazole + praziquantel to albendazole + praziquantel in school children 6-15 years and Salissou 2017 compared SP+AQ to nothing among children < 5 years.

Table 8: Prevalence of any anemia among children < 5 years, non-randomized studies

Study IDs	Country	Comparator	Age group	# of cycles	N	Prevalence ratio
Opoku 2016	Ghana	AL+alb+praz vs alb+praz	6-15 years	3	AL+alb+praz: 90 alb+praz:127	PR: 1.24 (95% CI 0.62-2.50)
Salissou 2017	Niger	SP+AQ vs nothing	3-59 mo	4	241 SMC, 241 control	PR: 1.0 (95% CI 0.25-3.95)

Prevalence of any anemia among children 5-9 years

Ndiaye 2019 reported any anemia among children 5-9 years, and noted a moderate effect of SMC on any anemia with five cycles of SP+AQ. (Grade: High)

Figure 15. Prevalence of any anemia among children 5-9 years, randomized studies

Prevalence of moderate anemia (hemoglobin < 8 mg/dL)

Six studies reported prevalence of moderate anemia (Hgb < 8 mg/dL) among children < 5 years. No studies reported moderate anemia among children ≥ 5 years.

Cisse 2016 (Senegal) and Sesay 2011 (Gambia) administered 3-4 cycles of SP+AQ to children < 5 years in low transmission zones and reported a small effect of SMC on any anemia, while Dicko 2011 (Mali) and Konate 2011 (Burkina Faso) administered 3-4 cycles of SP+AQ to children < 5 years in moderate to high transmission zones, and observed a significant protective effect on prevalence of moderate anemia. Within transmission strata, there was no heterogeneity. Kweku 2008 (Ghana) administered six cycles of AS-AQ and Tagbor 2016 (Ghana) administered five cycles of SP+AQ without significant protection from moderate anemia.

Among children < 5 years who received 3-4 cycles of SP+AQ, the evidence suggests that SMC protects against moderate anemia in zones of moderate to high transmission (Mali and Burkina Faso), but this effect was not observed in either study in Ghana, despite five cycles of AS-AQ (Kweku 2008) or SP+AQ (Tagbor 2016). In these sites, particularly Tagbor 2016 in southern Ghana, five cycles may not have been sufficient to cover the length of the transmission season.

The evidence suggests an effect of SMC on moderate anemia when administered for a duration adequate to the length of the transmission season in areas of moderate to high transmission, where malaria is a major driver of anemia in children < 5 years. (Grade: Moderate)

Figure 16. Prevalence of moderate anemia among children < 5 years, by transmission intensity, drug regimen, and 3-4 cycles vs 5-6 cycles, randomized studies

Prevalence of moderate anemia among children < 5 years in non-randomized studies

One study (Zongo 2015) reported moderate anemia among children < 5 years who received either three cycles of SP+AQ or DP to nothing. There was not an effect of SMC, either with SP+AQ or DP, in either arm.

Table 9: Prevalence of moderate anemia among children < 5 years, non-randomized studies

Study IDs	Country	Comparator	Age group	# of cycles	N	Prevalence ratio
Zongo 2015A	Burkina Faso	SP+AQ vs nothing	3-59 mo	3	742 SP+AQ, 250 control	PR = 1.14 (95% CI = 0.80-1.61)
Zongo 2015B	Burkina Faso	DP vs nothing	3-59 mo	3	757 DP, 250 control	PR = 1.04 (95% CI 0.73-1.48)

Prevalence of severe anemia

The two studies that reported severe anemia were from Senegal (Cisse 2016, Ndiaye 2019), and the prevalence was extremely low, resulting in large confidence intervals. Cisse 2016 reported results for < 5 years separately in 2008 and 2009. Only Ndiaye 2019 showed an effect for children < 5 years.

Table 10. Prevalence of severe anemia among children < 5 years and 5-9 years

Study IDs	Drug	Age group	# of cycles	Effect size
Cisse 2016	SP+AQ	<5 years	3	2008 PR: 0.30 (95% CI 0.07-1.19) 2009 PR: 2.14 (95% CI 0.93-4.9)
Ndiaye 2019	SP+AQ	<5 years	5	PR: 0.25 (0.07-0.87)
Cisse 2016b	SP+AQ	≥ 5 years	3	2009 PR: 1.01 (95% CI 0.44-2.33)*
Ndiaye 2019b	SP+AQ	≥ 5 years	5	PR: 0.84 (95% CI 0.22-2.24)

*2008 did not include children 5-9 years

Incidence of severe malaria

Three studies reported incidence of severe malaria among children < 5 years receiving 3-4 cycles of SP+AQ (Cisse 2016, Dicko 2011, and Konate 2011) and one study reported incidence of severe malaria among children 5-9 years receiving 3-4 cycles of SP+AQ (Cisse 2016). Overall heterogeneity was moderate. The effect was not significant in the study with baseline parasite prevalence < 5% (Cisse 2016). Data were not available from studies reporting other drug regimens or numbers of cycles. The evidence suggests an effect of SMC on reducing severe malaria among children < 5 years and among children 5-9 years. (Grade: High)

Figure 17. Incidence of severe malaria, children < 5 years vs 5-9 years, randomized studies

Incidence of severe malaria in non-randomized studies

Two studies reported incidence of severe malaria among children < 5 years receiving three to four cycles of SP+AQ (Issiaka 2020, Salissou), both based on reports by guardians of children during cross sectional surveys. Results from both studies were comparable to those found in randomized studies.

Table 11. Incidence of severe malaria among children < 5 years, non-randomized studies

Study ID	Country	Comparator	Age group	# of cycles	N	Risk ratio
Issiaka 2020	Mali	SP+AQ vs nothing	3-59 mo	4	2759 SMC, 3879 control	RR: 0.51 (95% CI 0.34–0.76)
Salissou 2017	Niger	SP+AQ vs nothing	3-59 mo	4	241 SMC, 241 control	RR: 0.28 (95% CI 0.19-0.42)

Incidence of hospitalization for any cause

Hospitalization for any cause was reported only for children < 5 years, in four studies, two among children < 5 years given three to four cycles of SP+AQ (Dicko 2011, Sesay 2011) in moderate transmission zones, one among children < 5 years given four cycles of SP+AQ in a high transmission zone (Konate 2011), and one among children < 5 years given six cycles of AS-AQ in a high transmission zone (Kweku 2008). Neither study in a low to moderate transmission zones demonstrated an effect, but both studies in higher transmission zones demonstrated an effect on all-cause hospitalizations, whether 3-4 cycles of SP+AQ or 5-6 cycles of AS-AQ. The evidence suggests that SMC has an effect on all-cause hospitalizations in higher transmission zones, where malaria admissions make up a substantial proportion of hospital admissions. (Grade: Moderate)

Figure 18. Incidence of all-cause hospitalization, by transmission intensity, drug regimen, and number of cycles, randomized studies

Incidence of hospitalization for any cause in non-randomized studies

Two studies reported incidence of severe malaria among children < 5 years receiving three to four cycles of SP+AQ (Issiaka 2020, Salissou), both based on reports by guardians of children during cross sectional surveys. While Issiaka 2020 reports results comparable to results from randomized studies, Salissou 2017 reports an effect larger than that of randomized studies.

Table 12. Incidence of all-cause hospitalization among children < 5 years, non-randomized studies

Study IDs	Country	Drug	Age group	# of cycles	N	Risk ratio
Issiaka 2020	Mali	SP+AQ vs nothing	3-59 mo	4	2759 SMC, 3879 control	RR: 0.58 (95% CI 0.41-0.81)
Salissou 2017	Niger	SP+AQ vs nothing	3-59 mo	4	241 SMC, 241 control	PR: 0.17 (95% CI 0.09-0.31)

All-cause mortality

All-cause mortality was reported both among children < 5 years and among children 5-9 years.

All-cause mortality among children < 5 years

Six studies reported all-cause mortality among children < 5 years, four studies among children < 5 years given three to four cycles of SP+AQ (Cisse 2016, Dicko 211, Konate 2011, Sesay 2011), one study among children < 5 years given five cycles of SP+AQ (Ndiaye 2016), and one study among children < 5 years given six cycles of AS-AQ. The evidence suggests that SMC is not associated with a reduction in all-cause mortality among children < 5 years. (Grade: Moderate)

Figure 19. All-cause mortality among children < 5 years, 3-4 cycles vs 5-6 cycles, randomized studies

All-cause mortality among children < 5 years in non-randomized studies

Three studies reported all-cause mortality among children < 5 years receiving 3-4 cycles of SMC in non-randomized designs, one that reported SP+AQ and DP (Zongo 2015), and two that reported SP+AQ Issiaka 2020, Salissou 2017). With the exception of the DP arm in Zongo 2015, the effect size was greater than that reported for randomized designs.

Table 13. Incidence of all-cause mortality among children < 5 years, non-randomized studies

Study IDs	Country	Comparator	Age group	# of cycles	N	Risk ratio
Zongo 2015A	Burkina Faso	SP+AQ vs nothing	3-59 mo	3	742 SP+AQ, 250 control	RR: 0.67 (95% CI 0.06-7.43)

Zongo 2015B	Burkina Faso	DP vs nothing	3-59 mo	3	757 DP, 250 control	RR: 1.32 (95% CI 0.5-11.82)
Issiaka 2020	Mali	SP+AQ vs nothing	3-59 mo	4	2759 SMC, 3879 control	RR 0.44 (95% CI 0.22-0.91)
Salissou 2017	Niger	SP+AQ vs nothing	3-59 mo	4	241 SMC, 241 control	RR: 0.54 (95% CI 0.22-1.33)

All-cause mortality among children 5-9 years

Two studies reported all-cause mortality among children 5-9 years, one study among children 5-9 years given three cycles of SP+AQ and one study among children 5-9 years given five cycles of SP+AQ, both in Senegal. Neither study demonstrated an effect of SMC on all-cause mortality, though both were in zones of low to moderate transmission.

It should be noted that in Ndiaye 2019, mortality reporters were operational in both SMC and control villages, and reported 12 deaths (among children < 5 years and children 5-9 years combined) in control villages and eight deaths in SMC villages. An additional six deaths were subsequently discovered in SMC villages when children who should have received SMC were not present (a similar effort to find all the children monthly was not conducted in the control arm). Given the difference in methods of death surveillance, in which an additional method was inadvertently used to identify deaths in the SMC arm, there was likely identification bias in the SMC arm, biasing toward no effect.

The evidence suggests that SMC is not associated with a reduction in all-cause mortality among children 5-9 years. (Grade: Low)

Figure 20. All-cause mortality among children 5-9 years, 3-4 cycles vs 5-6 cycles, randomized studies

Adverse events

Serious and severe adverse events

No severe adverse reactions related to the intervention were reported in the included studies.

Only Cisse 2016, which administered a total of 776,191 documented cycles over three years to children up to 120 months of age, reported serious or serious adverse events possibly related to the intervention. The five children in whom SAEs were reported did not receive SMC again. An independent review panel considered that only the extrapyramidal syndrome (4) was likely to be related to study drugs.

Table 14: Serious adverse events, Cisse 2016

	Age	Adverse event	Timing
1	9 yrs	Acute diarrheal disease leading to death	1 week after 1 st cycle
2	9 yrs	Rash and facial edema	2 days after 1 st cycle
3	5 yrs	Jaundice (yellow sclera, no liver tests done)*	2 days after 2 nd cycle
4	8 yrs	Extrapyramidal syndrome	2 days after 1 st cycle
5	17 mo	Skin rash (detected through active surveillance)**	2 weeks after 1 st cycle

*Child also took other medicines, including acetaminophen

**Dermatologists determined likely staphylococcal infection

Four studies (Cisse 2006, Dicko 2011, Konate 2011, Thera 2018) reported adverse events detected by active surveillance in individually randomized placebo-controlled trials, reporting adverse events in both placebo and SMC arms. Two studies (Dicko 2011, Konate 2011) administered four cycles of SP+AQ among children < 5 years, one study (Cisse 2006) administered three cycles of SP+AS among children < 5 years, and one study (Thera 2018) administered four cycles of SP+AQ among school children 6-15 years.

All four noted a marked trend or statistically significant increase in abdominal pain and/or nausea/vomiting in the intervention compared to the placebo arm. Thera 2018, in older children, also reported an increase in headaches in the intervention arm relative to the control arm. No other adverse event was statistically different between arms. This was consistent despite the substantial differences between studies in the proportion of cycles associated with adverse events. The evidence suggests that some mild to moderate adverse events, specifically nausea/vomiting/abdominal pain, are more common in children receiving SMC. (Grade: High)

Figure 21. Adverse events, SMC vs placebo, risk ratio, under active surveillance (three to four cycles SP+AQ among children < 5 years)

Table 15: Adverse events SMC vs placebo, per cycle, under active surveillance (three to four cycles SP+AQ among children < 5 years)

Study	Drug	Age	Surveillance type	Reporting	AEs / cycle SMC	AEs/cycle control	Any SAE?
Cisse 2006	SP+AS	2-59 mo	Active	By cycle	0.57 279/486	0.38 172/455	No
Dicko 2011	SP+AQ	3-59 mo	Active	By cycle	0.05 213/4319	0.04 161/4194	No
Konate 2011	SP+AQ	3-59 mo	Active	By cycle	0.19 769/4017	0.14 525/3771	No
Thera 2018	SP+AQ	6-15 yrs	Active	By cycle	0.55 219/400	0.37 146/400	No

Seven studies reported adverse events in a variety of other ways. Four cluster randomized trials (Ambe 2014, Cisse 2016, Ndiaye 2019, Tine 2014) were not placebo controlled and only reported adverse events in the SMC arm. Ambe 2020 conducted an end of season survey, Cisse 2016 and Ndiaye 2019 conducted enhanced passive surveillance, and Tine 2014 conducted active surveillance every cycle. Tagbor 2011, while a cluster randomized controlled trial, used the same drug (AS-AQ) for both prevention and treatment, and reported adverse events for both use as treatment and SMC, though with different sampling strategies for each. Ambe 2020, Kweku 2008, Sesay 2011 reported the proportion of children who reported an adverse event over the course of the season.

Table 16: Adverse events by design, placebo control, type of surveillance and reporting in studies without placebo control, results for placebo arm, and active surveillance

Study	Drug	Cycles	Age	Design	Placebo results	Surveillance type and reporting	AEs / cycle SMC	AEs/ cycle control	Any SAE?
Ambe 2020	SP+AQ	3-4	3-59 mo	cRCT	No	End of season survey, by subject	4.9% of children (10/204)	NA	No
Cisse 2016	SP+AQ	3-4	3-119 mo	stepped wedge	No	Passive, by cycle	0.002	NA	5

							924/471,282†		
Kweku 2008	AS-AQ	5-6	3-59 mo	iRCT	Yes	Passive, by subject	5.5% of children (36/650)	5.9% of children (37/626)	No
Ndiaye 2019	SP+AQ	5-6	3-119 mo	cRCT	No	Passive, by cycle	0.003 29/10,222	NA	No
Sesay 2011	SP+AQ	3-4	6-59 mo	iRCT	Unclear	Passive, by subject	1/639 children	NA	No
Tagbor 2011	AS-AQ	3-4	3-59 mo	cRCT	No*	Hybrid, by cycle and treatment course	Same drug for treatment and SMC, reported together		No
Tine 2014	SP+AQ	2*	3-119 mo	cRCT	No	Active, by cycle	0.20 190/973	NA	No

† 2010 adverse event data; adverse event data not reported for 2011

*Tine 2014: safety data from 2010 when only two rounds were done

Educational outcomes

One non-randomized study (Opoku 2016) compared AL+ albendazole + praziquantel (N=90) vs albendazole + praziquantel among school children (N = 127), administered as three cycles separated by three months (the AL + albendazole arm was not considered), and measured the effect on recall testing and sustained attention testing. Improvement in code transmission test (CTT) score (sustained attention) was 20.5% in the AL+ albendazole + praziquantel arm compared to 5.75% in the albendazole + praziquantel arm, a rate ratio of 3.57. Mean recall test scores improved 27.9% in the AL+ albendazole + praziquantel arm compared to 18.3% in the albendazole + praziquantel arm, a rate ratio of 1.52.

Discussion

Summary of main results

Effect on malaria incidence: Seasonal malaria chemoprevention, regardless of transmission setting, age < 5 years or age 5-9 years, whether given in three to four cycles or five to six cycles, and regardless of drug regimen, reduced incidence of confirmed clinical malaria illness. Among studies that administered SMC to children < 10 years of age and reported incidence separately for children < 5 years and children 5-9 years, there was no difference in effect size between children < 5 years and children 5-9 years. (Grade: Moderate)

Effect on malaria prevalence: Seasonal malaria chemoprevention, regardless of transmission setting, age < 5 years or age 5-9 years, whether given in three to four cycles or five to six cycles, and regardless of drug regimen, reduced prevalence of malaria infection in end of season surveys. (Grade: Moderate)

Effect on prevalence of any anemia: Seasonal malaria chemoprevention, administered as SP+AQ, resulted in a small reduction in prevalence of any anemia (hemoglobin < 11mg/dL) in end of season surveys among both children < 5 years and

children 5-9 years. Moderate effects were seen in the studies with the highest baseline parasite prevalence (>40%). (Grade: Moderate)

Effect on prevalence of moderate anemia: Seasonal malaria chemoprevention, administered as SP+AQ, resulted in a modest reduction in prevalence of moderate anemia (hemoglobin < 8 mg/dL) in end of season surveys among children < 5 years in moderate to high transmission zones (baseline parasite prevalence > 10%). (Grade: Moderate)

Effect on incidence of severe malaria: Seasonal malaria chemoprevention, administered as SP+AQ in three to four cycles reduced incidence of severe malaria among both children < 5 years and children 5-9 years, in studies in which baseline parasite prevalence was > 2%. (Grade: High)

Effect on incidence of all cause hospitalization: Seasonal malaria chemoprevention reduced all-cause hospitalization in the two studies in which baseline parasite prevalence was \geq 20%. (Grade: Moderate)

Effect on incidence of all-cause mortality: Seasonal malaria chemoprevention had no effect on all-cause mortality. (Grade: Low)

Effect on adverse events: Seasonal malaria chemoprevention has very low risk of serious or severe adverse events, < 1/100,000 cycles. Nausea, vomiting, and abdominal pain are more frequent in children who receive SMC than placebo. (Grade: High)

Expansion of age range to children 5-9 years: While primarily conducted in Senegal, studies including children < 10 years comparing effect size among children < 5 years with that in children 5-9 years found no difference in effect size for incidence, prevalence, any anemia, and severe malaria. All-cause hospitalization and all-cause mortality were not reported for children 5-9 years.

Increase in number of cycles: Studies in zones with a shorter transmission season generally used three to four cycles, while studies in zones with longer transmission seasons generally used five to six cycles, thus making direct comparison challenging, however, studies that used five to six cycles in zones with longer transmission seasons achieved comparable results to those seen with three to four cycles in zones with shorter transmission seasons.

Agreements and disagreements with other studies or reviews

The ACCESS-SMC Partnership published information on SMC scale up in 2015 and 2016 in Burkina Faso, Chad, Gambia, Guinea, Mali, Niger, and Nigeria, including a case control study to monitor protective efficacy in the programmatic setting. In data collected from Burkina Faso in 2016, Chad in 2016, Gambia in 2015 and 2016, Mali in 2015 and 2016 and Nigeria in 2016, among 2,185 confirmed cases and 4,370 controls, a random effects meta-analysis found a protective effectiveness against clinical malaria incidence

in the first 28 days from a cycle of 88% (pooled OR 0.12, 95% CI 0.06-0.21), and in days 29-42 from a cycle of 61% (pooled OR 0.39, 95% CI 0.28-0.53). [12,13]

Scale up reports have also reported serious and severe adverse events reported from the health system. Senegal reported that from the first three years of SMC (2014-2016), covering over 5 million cycles, one case of Lyell syndrome, two cases of Stevens-Johnson syndrome, one case of extra-pyramidal syndrome, and three allergic reactions [14]. The ACCESS-SMC Partnership reported 36 serious adverse events in over 37.5 million cycles in 2015 and 2016, one with rash, two with fever, one with extra-pyramidal syndrome, one with Quincke's edema, and 31 with gastrointestinal conditions [12].

After the literature search and data abstraction were completed, Chandramohan and colleagues published the results of a study comparing SMC to the RTS,S vaccine to SMC+RTS,S. In this three arm individually randomized controlled trial, 6861 children aged 5-17 months were randomized to SP+AQ (2287), RTS,S (2288), or SMC+ RTS,S (2286). Of these, 1965, 1988, and 1967 respectively, received the first dose and were followed for three years. Incidence was 305 per 1000 person-years in the SMC arm, 278 per 1000 person-years in the RTS,S arm, and 113 per 1000 person-years in the SMC+RTS,S arm. SMC + RTS,S vs RTS,S was 59.6% (95% CI 54.7 to 64.0) effective against clinical malaria, 70.6% (95% CI, 42.3 to 85.0) effective against hospital admission with severe malaria, and 75.3% (95% CI, 12.5 to 93.0) effective against mortality due to malaria [15].

Disclaimer

The findings and conclusions in this paper are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.

Table 17: Reason for exclusion of excluded studies

Study	Title	reason for exclusion
Abiola 2015	Impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in the production of msp1 the ama1 antibodies in Senegal	no outcomes
Ahorlu 2009	Effectiveness of intermittent preventive treatment for children (IPTC) combined with timely treatment at home for malaria control	intervention: year round
Ahorlu 2009	Effectiveness of combined intermittent preventive treatment for children and timely home treatment for malaria control	intervention: year round
Ahorlu 2011	Two-year evaluation of Intermittent Preventive Treatment for Children (IPTc) combined with timely home treatment for malaria control in Ghana	duplicate
Aikins 2017	COST-EFFECTIVENESS OF SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION IN UPPER WEST REGION OF GHANA	no outcomes
Alexander 2007	Modelling the impact of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria on selection pressure for drug resistance	modeling
Angoran-Benie 2019	Community-based approach to reach malnourished infants from 6 months to 5 years during a seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) campaign in remote areas in Niger	intervention: SMC+nutrition
Anne 2018	Strategy for improving the treatment of seasonal malaria chemoprevention among children from 3 to 120 months of age in goudomp health district, Senegal: A 3-day directly observed treatment initiative	no outcomes
Anne 2019	Seasonal malaria chimio prevention 2017 in the health district of goudomp Senegal costeffectiveness analysis of two treatment strategies for children aged 3-120 months	no outcomes
Anonymous 2016	Corrigendum: Impact of combined intermittent preventive treatment of malaria and helminths on anaemia, sustained attention, and recall in Northern Ghanaian schoolchildren	link to 1171 - I correction of outcome
Anonymous 2016	Correction: safety of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention (SMC) with sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine plus amodiaquine when delivered to children under 10 years of age by district health services in senegal: results from a stepped-wedge cluster randomized trial (PLoS ONE (2016) 11: 10 (e0162563) DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0162563)	link to included

Ansah 2016	Evaluation of the impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention on mortality and mortality in young children in Northern Ghana	design: one cluster per arm
Ansah 2016	Evaluation of the impact of implementation of seasonal malaria chemoprevention on morbidity and mortality in young children: A qualitative study in Northern Ghana	no outcomes
Antwi 2016	Facilitators and Barriers to Uptake of an Extended Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention Programme in Ghana: A Qualitative Study of Caregivers and Community Health Workers	no outcomes
Attaher 2016	Influence of seasonal malaria chemoprevention on markers of T cell exhaustion and immunoregulation	no outcomes
Attaher 2020	Effect of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention on Immune Markers of Exhaustion and Regulation	no outcomes
Ba 2014	Extending the age range for seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC): Effectiveness of SMC in children under 10 years of age delivered through the district health service in Senegal	link to included
Ba 2018	Implementation, coverage and equity of large-scale door-to-door delivery of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention (SMC) to children under 10 in Senegal	no outcomes
Barger 2009	Intermittent preventive treatment using artemisinin-based combination therapy reduces malaria morbidity among school-aged children in Mali	intervention: < 3 cycles
Barry 2016	Comparison of three versus four rounds of seasonal malaria chemoprevention on the incidence of clinical malaria in mali	no control - compares 3 vs 4 cycles
Barry 2018	Optimal mode for delivery of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Ouelessebouyou, Mali: A cluster randomized trial	no outcomes
Beeson 2011	Intermittent preventive treatment to reduce the burden of malaria in children: new evidence on integration and delivery	no primary data
Beshir 2016	Baseline frequencies of molecular markers of drug resistance before scaling-up access to seasonal malaria chemoprevention in seven countries across the sahel	no outcomes
Beshir 2017	Baseline molecular data before scaling-up of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in seven countries across the Sahel	no outcomes
Bicaba 2020	Longitudinal analysis of the capacities of community health workers mobilized for seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Burkina Faso	no outcomes

Bigira 2012	Assessing the association between malaria chemoprevention and the nutritional status of a cohort of young african children	not seasonal
Bigira 2014	Protective efficacy and safety of three antimalarial regimens for the prevention of malaria in young Ugandan children: a randomized controlled trial	not seasonal
Bisanzio 2019	The effectiveness of seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) in the operational programming context of Guinea	no outcomes
Bojang 2008	A randomised trial to compare the safety, tolerability and efficacy of three drug combinations for intermittent preventive treatment in children	duplicate
Bojang 2009	A Study of intermittent preventive treatment and home based management of malaria in a rural area of The Gambia	link to included
Bojang 2010	A randomised trial to compare the safety, tolerability and efficacy of three drug combinations for intermittent preventive treatment in children	no control - compares drug regimens
Bojang 2011	Two strategies for the delivery of IPTc in an area of seasonal malaria transmission in the Gambia: a randomised controlled trial	no control - compares VHW vs RCH trekkers for delivery
Bonkougou 2018	Seasonal malaria chemoprevention, an effective intervention for reducing malaria morbidity and mortality	no control
Bonkougou 2019	Using seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) to screen for acute malnutrition	no outcomes
Boulanger 2010	Immunological consequences of intermittent preventive treatment against malaria in Senegalese preschool children	no outcomes
Brune 2017	Seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Ankililoaka, Madagascar	no control
Cairns 2010	Amodiaquine dosage and tolerability for intermittent preventive treatment to prevent malaria in children	no outcomes
Cairns 2012	Estimating the potential public health impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in African children	modeling
Cairns 2015	Analysis of Preventive Interventions for Malaria: Exploring Partial and Complete Protection and Total and Primary Intervention Effects	no control - SMC vs IPTi
Cairns 2015	Randomised controlled trial: Monthly malaria chemoprevention shows potential in an area of very high, perennial malaria transmission	no primary data

Cairns 2016	Optimizing seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) in africa: Estimating the impact of increasing the number of smc cycles on the number of children protected, the malaria burden and cost-effectiveness	modeling
Cairns 2017	Monitoring the protective efficacy of seasonal malaria chemoprevention using case-control studies: Methodology and results from 5 countries	case control
Cairns 2019	Effectiveness of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in areas of intense, seasonal malaria transmission: Secondary analysis of data from a household-randomized clinical trial in burkina faso and mali	intervention: SMC+AZ
Cairns 2019	The duration of protection from azithromycin against malaria, pneumonia and gastroenteritis when given alongside seasonal malaria chemoprevention: Secondary analysis of data from a clinical trial in Hounde, Burkina Faso and Bougouni, Mali	intervention: SMC+AZ
Cairns 2020	Evaluation of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in two areas of intense seasonal malaria transmission: Secondary analysis of a household-randomised, placebo-controlled trial in Hounde District, Burkina Faso and Bougouni District, Mali	intervention: SMC+AZ
CairnsMatthew 2015	Monthly malaria chemoprevention shows potential in an area of very high, perennial malaria transmission	duplicate
Camara 2018	Perception of the mothers and the child minders of the region of sedhiou on the seasonal malaria chemoprevention in 2017: Are the absences and the diseases of the children - No cases of disguised refusals?	no outcomes
Ceesay 2016	Implementation of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in the gambia	no outcomes
Ceesay 2017	IMPLEMENTATION OF SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION IN THE GAMBIA	no outcomes
Chandramohan 2019	Effect of Adding Azithromycin to Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention	intervention: SMC+AZ
Chatio 2019	Community acceptability of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention of morbidity and mortality in young children: A qualitative study in the Upper West Region of Ghana	no outcomes
Cisse 2009	Randomized trial of piperazine with sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine or dihydroartemisinin for malaria intermittent preventive treatment in children	no control - compares drug regimens

Clarke 2008	Effect of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria on health and education in schoolchildren: a cluster-randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial	not seasonal
Clarke 2014	Seasonal malaria chemoprevention and micronutrient supplementation in early childhood: Effect on asymptomatic parasitaemia, anemia and Cognition	intervention: SMC+nutrition
Clarke 2015	Seasonal malaria chemoprevention combined with micronutrient supplementation delivered through community preschools: Findings from a cluster randomized trial in Mali	intervention: SMC+nutrition
Clarke 2016	Impact of micronutrient supplementation combined with malaria chemoprevention on malaria, anaemia and cognitive development in early childhood: Findings from a cluster randomized study in southern mali	intervention: SMC+nutrition
Clarke 2017	Impact of a malaria intervention package in schools on Plasmodium infection, anaemia and cognitive function in schoolchildren in Mali: a pragmatic cluster-randomised trial	intervention: < 3 cycles
Clarke 2017	IMPACT OF MICRONUTRIENT SUPPLEMENTATION COMBINED WITH MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION ON MALARIA, ANAEMIA AND COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT IN EARLY CHILDHOOD: FINDINGS FROM A CLUSTER RANDOMIZED STUDY IN SOUTHERN MALI	intervention: SMC+nutrition
Coldiron 2016	Safety and tolerability of dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine as intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in a refugee camp, adjumani, Uganda	not seasonal
Coldiron 2017	PROTECTIVE EFFECTIVENESS OF SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION IN NIGER: A PROSPECTIVE CASECONTROL STUDY	case control
Coldiron 2017	Prevalence of parasitemia in an area receiving SMC	no control
Coldiron 2017	Prevalence of parasitemia during two seasons in an area receiving seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) in Niger	no control
Coldiron 2017	Intermittent preventive treatment for malaria among children in a refugee camp in Northern Uganda: lessons learned	not seasonal
Coldiron 2019	Clinical diagnostic evaluation of HRP2 and pLDH-based rapid diagnostic tests for malaria in an area receiving seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Niger	no control - comparison of RDTs
Compaore 2011	Efficacy of dihydroartemisinin plus piperaquin compared to amodiaquin plus sulfadoxin/pyrimethamin in seasonal IPT of malaria in	link to included

	children in a rural area of Bobo-Dioulasso (Burkina Faso)	
Compaore 2017	Association of malaria and anemia with malnutrition in children following a seasonal malaria chemoprevention program in a rural area of burkina faso	no control
Compaore 2017	Evaluation of the implementation fidelity of the seasonal malaria chemoprevention intervention in Kaya health district, Burkina Faso	no outcomes
Conteh 2010	Cost effectiveness of seasonal intermittent preventive treatment using amodiaquine & artesunate or sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine in Ghanaian children	no outcomes
Danquah 2012	Reduced efficacy of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in malnourished children (Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy (2009) 53, 5 (1753-1759))	intervention: IPTi
Diallo 2014	Pharmacovigilance during campaign of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Senegal, 2013	no outcomes
Diallo 2016	Active monitoring of pharmacovigilance at community level during the seasonal malaria chemoprevention campaign in the health district kolda senegal, 2015	no control - compares pharmacovigilance
Diallo 2017	Monitoring seasonal malaria chemoprevention campaigns: lessons learned from coverage surveys in 7 countries	no outcomes
Diallo 2018	Monitoring of pharmacovigilance during the seasonal malaria chemoprevention campaign in Senegal, 2013 to 2017	no outcomes
Diarra 2015	Qualitative Research to Inform the Implementation of Home Fortification with Nutrition Education with Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention through Early Childhood Development Centres for Children Aged 6-59 Months in Sikasso, Mali	no outcomes
Diarra 2017	Impact of micronutrient powders combined with malaria chemoprevention on anemia, malaria and cognitive development: A cluster-randomized study in malian children	intervention: SMC+nutrition
Diarra 2018	Impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention on malaria transmission on two sites of therapeutic efficacy study in Mali	no control
Diarra 2019	Molecular studies of PfDHPS and PfDHFR during seasonal malaria chemoprevention at three study sites in Mali	no outcomes
Diawara 2015	Measuring the impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention as part of routine malaria control in Kita Mali	no control

Diawara 2017	Measuring the impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention as part of routine malaria control in Kita, Mali	design: one cluster per arm
Diawara 2017	FAILURE OF AVAILABLE MALARIA CONTROL INTERVENTIONS IN DANGASSA, MALI: CONTINUOUSLY HIGH PREVALENCE OF PLASMODIUM FALCIPARUM INFECTION IN A COHORT OF 1,400 INDIVIDUALS FROM 2012 TO 2015	no control
Diawara 2019	Impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention among children five to ten years of age in kita and bafoulabe districts, mali	abstract only
Dicko 2008	Impact of intermittent preventive treatment with sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine targeting the transmission season on the incidence of clinical malaria in children in Mali	intervention: < 3 cycles
Dicko 2011	Malaria morbidity in children in the year after they had received intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in Mali: a randomized control trial	link to included
Dicko 2016	A trial of seasonal malaria chemoprevention plus azithromycin in African children	protocol
Dieng 2019	Contrasting Asymptomatic and Drug Resistance Gene Prevalence of Plasmodium falciparum in Ghana: Implications on Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention	no outcomes
Ding 2020	Adherence and Population Pharmacokinetic Properties of Amodiaquine When Used for Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention in African Children	no outcomes
Diouf 2015	Seasonal malaria chemoprevention implementation in children from three to 120 months experience in the four southern regions in Senegal	no outcomes
Druetz 2017	Seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Burkina Faso protects children against malaria and anaemia under routine program implementation	inappropriate control
Druetz 2018	Impact Evaluation of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention under Routine Program Implementation: A Quasi-Experimental Study in Burkina Faso	inappropriate control
Druetz 2018	Evaluation of direct and indirect effects of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Mali	no control
Esch 2018	Estimating the health impact of a seasonal malaria chemoprevention intervention in mali in 2017: Modeling deaths averted, cases averted and disability adjusted life years (DALYS) averted	modeling

Esch 2019	Prospectively estimating the health impact of upcoming president's malaria initiative impact malaria project-supported seasonal malaria chemoprevention campaigns in 70 districts across niger, mali and Cameroon in 2019	modeling
Fabrice 2010	Prevalence and selection of Plasmodium falciparum drug resistance molecular markers under intermittent preventive therapy in Burkina Faso	no outcomes
Fabrice 2011	Plasmodium falciparum drug resistance molecular markers under intermittent preventive therapy with dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine (DP) vs. amodiaquine-sulfadoxine/pyrimethamine (AQ-SP) in Burkina Faso	no outcomes
Geerligs 2003	Analysis of the effects of malaria chemoprophylaxis in children on haematological responses, morbidity and mortality	review
Grais 2018	Molecular markers of resistance to amodiaquine plus sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine in an area with seasonal malaria chemoprevention in south central Niger	no outcomes
Gueye 2018	Decrease of malaria burden among children under five years and other age groups in SMC regions in Senegal	no control
Guillebaud 2013	Epidemiology of malaria in an area of seasonal transmission in Niger and implications for the design of a seasonal malaria chemoprevention strategy	no outcomes
Hulle 2016	Implementing seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) in the context of ebola virus disease (evd) in guinea	no control
Humphreys 2018	Spatiotemporal modelling of prevalence of plasmodium falciparum drug resistance mutations in the DHPS gene across Africa, 1990 - 2015	modeling
Issiaka 2015	Determining the optimal mode for delivery of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Mali	no outcomes
Issiaka 2017	Impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention on hospital admissions and mortality in children under 5 years in ouelessebougou, Mali	link to included
Jagannathan 2016	Effective Antimalarial Chemoprevention in Childhood Enhances the Quality of CD4+ T Cells and Limits Their Production of Immunoregulatory Interleukin 10	no outcomes
Jean 2012	Seasonal malaria chemoprevention and community case management for malaria in Southern senegal: A cluster-randomized trial	no outcomes
Kaly 2018	Knowledge, attitudes and practices of mothers caretakers of children aged 3 to 120 months on of	no outcomes

	seasonal malaria chemo prevention in bounkiling health district, South Senegal	
Kamate 2017	Scaling up seasonal malaria chemoprevention in mali: Implementation challenges and lessons learned	no control
Kanya 2020	The Impact of Control Interventions on Malaria Burden in Young Children in a Historically High-Transmission District of Uganda: A Pooled Analysis of Cohort Studies from 2007 to 2018	not seasonal
Kana 2017	Scaling-up of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in sokoto and zamfara states, Nigeria: Monitoring delivery and impact	no outcomes
Katile 2019	Malaria parasitemia incidence among different age groups in a stable transmission area of Mali receiving seasonal malaria chemoprevention	no control
Kobbe 2011	Follow-up survey of children who received sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine for intermittent preventive antimalarial treatment in infants	intervention: IPTi
Kombate 2019	Analysis of the quality of seasonal malaria chemoprevention provided by community health Workers in Boulsa health district, Burkina Faso	no outcomes
Konate 2011	Morbidity from malaria in children in the year after they had received intermittent preventive treatment of malaria: a randomised trial	link to included
Konate 2019	Effect of seasonal malaria chemoprevention on malaria in children under 5 years: A cohort study in Dangassa, Mali	no control
Konate 2020	Effect of routine seasonal malaria chemoprevention on malaria trends in children under 5 years in Dangassa, Mali	no control
Koscalova 2015	Monitoring the protective effect and the effectiveness of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Niger	inappropriate control
Koscalova 2017	Malaria incidence in the area of seasonal malaria chemoprevention	case control
Kpormegbe 2014	The role of community participation in intermittent preventive treatment of childhood malaria in southeastern Ghana	no outcomes
Kweku 2009	Options for the delivery of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria to children: a community randomised trial	no outcomes
Kweku 2011	Assessment of the efficacy, tolerability and ease of administration of dihydroartemisinin plus piperazine and artesunate plus sulfamethoxypyrazine plus pyrimethamine compared with sulphadoxine-	no control

	pyrimethamine for preventing malaria in Ghanaian children	
Lasry 2015	Seasonal malaria chemoprevention, three years of implementation	no control
LeMenach 2015	Combining nutritional supplementation with seasonal malaria chemoprevention in nigeria decreases the odds of confirmed clinical malaria: Findings from a case-control study	intervention: SMC+nutrition
Lo 2011	Impact of seasonal intermittent preventive treatment in children: Molecular markers of resistance in three health districts in Senegal	no outcomes
Lo 2012	Prevalence of mutation of pfcr1 after the use of amodiaquine in intermittent preventive treatment in children (IPTC) in Senegal	no outcomes
Lo 2013	Prevalence of molecular markers of drug resistance in an area of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in children in Senegal	no outcomes
Mahamar 2016	Seasonal malaria chemoprevention is associated with a reduction in seropositivity to blood-stage antigens	no outcomes
Mahamar 2017	Effect of seasonal malaria chemoprevention on the acquisition of antibodies to Plasmodium falciparum antigens in Ouelessebougou, Mali	no outcomes
Mahamar 2019	Long-term effect of seasonal malaria chemoprevention with amodiaquine plus sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine on molecular markers of resistance in ouelessebougou, Mali	no outcomes
Mahamar 2019	Effect of four years of seasonal malaria chemoprevention on the acquisition of antibodies to plasmodium falciparum antigens in ouelessebougou, Mali	no outcomes
Maiga 2014	School performance after intermittent preventive treatment using artemisinin-based combination	intervention: < 3 cycles
Maiga 2016	Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention with Sulphadoxine-Pyrimethamine and Amodiaquine Selects Pfdhfr-dhps Quintuple Mutant Genotype in Mali	no outcomes
Maiga 2018	Selection of seven-mutation Pfcr1-Pfmdr1 genotype after scaling seasonal malaria chemoprevention with sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine and amodiaquine in Mali	no outcomes
Maiteki 2015	School-based treatment with act to reduce transmission' (start-IPT): Evaluation of the community impact of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in Ugandan children	not seasonal

Maiteki-Sebuguzi 2017	EVALUATING THE COMMUNITY-LEVEL IMPACT OF INTERMITTENT PREVENTIVE TREATMENT OF SCHOOLCHILDREN FOR MALARIA IN JINJA, UGANDA: A CLUSTER-RANDOMIZED TRIAL	not seasonal
Matangila 2015	Efficacy and safety of intermittent preventive treatment with sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (SP) and SP-piperaquine in schoolchildren in Kinshasa, The Democratic Republic of the Congo (RDC)	not seasonal
Matangila 2015	Efficacy and safety of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in schoolchildren: a systematic review	review
Matangila 2017	The perception of parents and teachers about intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in school children in a semi-rural area of Kinshasa, in the Democratic Republic of Congo	not seasonal
Matangila 2017	Efficacy and safety of intermittent preventive treatment in schoolchildren with sulfadoxine/pyrimethamine (SP) and SP plus piperaquine in Democratic Republic of the Congo: a randomised controlled trial	not seasonal
Meremikwu 2005	Chemoprophylaxis and intermittent treatment for preventing malaria in children	review
Meremikwu 2008	Chemoprophylaxis and intermittent treatment for preventing malaria in children	review
Meremikwu 2012	Intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in children living in areas with seasonal transmission	review
Moroso 2017	Transforming the malaria landscape: Results from a threeyear implementation research project expanding access to seasonal malaria chemoprevention in seven Sahelian countries (ACCESS-SMC)	case control
Muhindo 2017	Intermittent preventive treatment with dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine in young Ugandan children in the setting of indoor residual spraying of insecticide	not seasonal
Namirimu 2013	Impact of chemoprevention on the development of t cell responses to malaria	not seasonal
Nankabirwa 2010	Efficacy, safety, and tolerability of three regimens for prevention of malaria: a randomized, placebo-controlled trial in Ugandan schoolchildren	not seasonal
Nankabirwa 2014	Impact of intermittent preventive treatment with dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine on malaria in Ugandan schoolchildren: a randomized, placebo-controlled trial	not seasonal

National Institute for Medical Research 2020	Evaluation of the Implementation and Effectiveness of Intermittent Preventive Treatment for Malaria Using Dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine on Reducing Malaria Burden in School Aged Children in Tanzania	not seasonal
Nayiga 2015	Lessons for integrating intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in school systems in low income settings: Experiences from Uganda	not seasonal
Nct 2005	Study of the Impact of Intermittent Preventive Treatment in Schools on Malaria, Anaemia and Education	protocol
Nct 2014	A Trial of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention Plus Azithromycin in African Children	protocol
Nct 2017	Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention With or Without Lipid-based Nutrient Supplement in Children Aged 6-59 Months in Mali	protocol
Nct 2019	Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention With Dihydroartemisin Piperaquin vs. Sulfadoxine-pyrimethamin+Amodiaquin	protocol
Ndiaye 2011	Costing a large-scale implementation of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in children delivered through community health workers in Senegal	no outcomes
Ndiaye 2011	Impact of intermittent preventive treatment in children (IPTC) on Plasmodium falciparum infections complexity: Resistance markers and kinetic of antibodies against P. falciparum in Senegal	no outcomes
Ndiaye 2011	Monitoring of drug resistance after intermittent preventive treatment for infants and children (IPTI/C) in Senegal	no outcomes
Ndiaye 2011	Safety of seasonal intermittent preventive treatment against malaria with sulfadoxine pyrimethamine + amodiaquine when delivered to children under ten years of age by district health staff in Senegal	no outcomes
Ndiaye 2012	Costing a large-scale implementation of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in children delivered through community health workers in senegal	no outcomes
Ndiaye 2013	Evaluation of the tolerance of sulfadoxinepyrimethamine + amodiaquine combination in seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) combined with home based management (HMM) in children under 10 years in Senegal	link to included
Ndiaye 2013	Selection of antimalarial drug resistance after intermittent preventive treatment of infants and children (IPTi/c) in Senegal	no outcomes

Ndiaye 2013	Seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Senegal: From research to policy	no outcomes
Ndiaye 2014	Potential impact of intermittent preventive treatment (IPT) on the acquisition of antibodies to malaria antigens GLURP-R0 and AMA-1 in senegalese children	no outcomes
Ndiaye 2015	Evaluation of the impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention administered by mass campaign in Southern Senegal	case control
Ndiaye 2015	Potential Impact of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention on the Acquisition of Antibodies Against Glutamate-Rich Protein and Apical Membrane Antigen 1 in Children Living in Southern Senegal	no outcomes
Ndiaye 2016	Impact evaluation after three years of seasonal malaria chemoprevention implementation by mass campaigns in southern senegal	case control
Ndiaye 2016	Safety of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention (SMC) with Sulfadoxine-Pyrimethamine plus Amodiaquine when Delivered to Children under 10 Years of Age by District Health Services in Senegal: Results from a Stepped-Wedge Cluster Randomized Trial	link to included
Ndiaye 2016	Trends of high reduction of malaria cases in sedhiou district following seasonal malaria chemoprevention first campaign: Lessons learned	no control
Ndiaye 2016	IMMUNOLOGICAL EFFECT OF SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION (SMC) WITH SULFADOXINEPYRIMETHAMINE (SP) AND AMODIAQUINE (AQ) IN CHILDREN UNDER 10 YEARS IN THE SOUTHEASTERN PART OF SENEGAL	no outcomes
Ndiaye 2017	IMPACT EVALUATION AFTER THREE YEARS OF SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION IMPLEMENTATION BY MASS CAMPAIGNS IN SOUTHERN SENEGAL	case control
Ndiaye 2017	TRENDS OF HIGH REDUCTION OF MALARIA CASES IN SEDHIOU DISTRICT FOLLOWING SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION FIRST CAMPAIGN: LESSONS LEARNED	no control
Ndiaye 2017	Impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention after 3 years at scale in Southern Senegal	no control
Ndiaye 2018	Evaluation of Two Strategies for Community-Based Safety Monitoring during Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention Campaigns in Senegal, Compared with the National Spontaneous Reporting System	no outcomes

Ndiop 2015	Tracking the impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention on morbidity and mortality of children in senegal through the routine health information system	no control
Ndiop 2017	Has seasonal malaria chemoprevention decreased the malaria burden among children under five years in Senegal?	no control
Nonvignon 2016	Cost-effectiveness of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in upper west region of Ghana	no outcomes
Noor 2015	Sub-National Targeting of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention in the Sahelian Countries of the Nouakchott Initiative	modeling
Ntab 2007	Impact of intermittent preventive anti-malarial treatment on the growth and nutritional status of preschool children in rural Senegal (west Africa)	no outcomes
Obiero 2019	The effect of adding azithromycin to the antimalarials (sulphadoxine/pyrimethamine and amodiaquine) used for seasonal malaria chemoprevention on the immune response to plasmodium falciparum	no outcomes
Okuneye 2019	Using models to inform implementation policies of seasonal malaria chemoprevention	modeling
Oresanya 2019	An assessment of quality of delivery of seasonal malaria chemoprevention using low literate community health workers in nigeria	no outcomes
Ouedraogo 2016	Impact of seasonal malaria chemoprophylaxis in a high and seasonal malaria transmission setting in burkina faso	modeling
Ouedraogo 2016	Effective scaling-up of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in burkina faso	no outcomes
Ouedraogo 2017	Understanding and optimizing operational seasonal malaria chemoprevention through data analysis and modeling: The example of Burkina Faso	modeling
Ouedraogo 2017	EFFECTIVE SCALING-UP OF SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION IN BURKINA FASO	no outcomes
Pactr 2013	An integrated malaria control strategy including community case management and Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention in Senegal	protocol
Pactr 2014	Randomized open-label trial to evaluate the efficacy of artesunate-amodiaquin for seasonal malaria chemoprevention in suburban school of Bamako, Sirak	protocol
Patouillard 2011	Coverage, adherence and costs of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in children employing different delivery strategies in Jasikan, Ghana	no outcomes

Pitt 2012	Intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in children: a qualitative study of community perceptions and recommendations in Burkina Faso and Mali	no outcomes
Pitt 2015	Delivering seasonal malaria chemoprevention to children under ten at scale in central Senegal: Costs and cost determinants	no outcomes
Pitt 2017	Large-scale delivery of seasonal malaria chemoprevention to children under 10 in Senegal: an economic analysis	no outcomes
Rehman 2019	Intermittent preventive treatment of malaria delivered to primary schoolchildren provided effective individual protection in Jinja, Uganda: secondary outcomes of a cluster-randomized trial (START-IPT)	not seasonal
Roger 2011	Impact of combining intermittent preventive treatment with home management of malaria in children under ten years, in a rural area of Senegal	intervention: < 3 cycles
Rohner 2010	In a randomized controlled trial of iron fortification, anthelmintic treatment, and intermittent preventive treatment of malaria for anemia control in Ivorian children, only anthelmintic treatment shows modest benefit	intervention: < 3 cycles
Sagara 2016	Coverage of seasonal malaria chemoprevention delivered by mobile teams at fixed points in 14 districts in mali, through Access-Smc	no outcomes
Sagara 2017	A TRIAL OF SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION PLUS AZITHROMYCIN IN AFRICAN CHILDREN	intervention: SMC+AZ
Sagara 2017	Seasonal malaria chemoprevention scaling up and its impact assessment in Mali	no control
Sagara 2017	COVERAGE OF SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION DELIVERED BY MOBILE TEAMS AT FIXED POINTS IN 14 DISTRICTS IN MALI, THROUGH ACCESS-SMC	no outcomes
Sagara 2018	Seasonal malaria chemoprevention scaling up in Mali: Coverage and impact on malaria burdern and markers of the resistance of plasmodium falciparum to sulfadoxine pyrimethamine and amodiaquine	no control
Salam 2014	Impact of community-based interventions for the prevention and control of malaria on intervention coverage and health outcomes for the prevention and control of malaria	review
Salissou 2016	Perception de la chimioprevention du paludisme saisonnier au Niger	duplicate

Salissou 2016	Perception of the seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Niger	no outcomes
Sangare 2019	Seasonal malaria chemoprevention and compliance during four monthly treatments with sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine and amodiaquine at 3 study sites in Mali	no outcomes
Saye 2015	Malaria chemoprevention, undernutrition and anaemia in children: Findings from three randomized intervention trials in Southern Mali	intervention: SMC+nutrition
Shehu 2017	Malaria preventive practices and acceptability of seasonal malaria chemoprevention among caregivers of under five children in rural and urban communities of Kano, Nigeria, 2017	no outcomes
Sokhna 2008	A trial of the efficacy, safety and impact on drug resistance of four drug regimens for seasonal intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in Senegalese children	no control - comparison of 4 regimens
Some 2014	Selection of drug resistance-mediating Plasmodium falciparum genetic polymorphisms by seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Burkina Faso	no outcomes
Soumare 2017	SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION IS ASSOCIATED WITH A REDUCTION IN SEROPOSITIVITY TO BLOOD-STAGE ANTIGENS	no outcomes
Staedke 2018	Assessment of community-level effects of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in schoolchildren in Jinja, Uganda (START-IPT trial): a cluster-randomised trial	not seasonal
Strachan 2016	The use of formative research to inform the design of a seasonal malaria chemoprevention intervention in northern Nigeria	no outcomes
Sundell 2015	Variable piperazine exposure significantly impacts protective efficacy of monthly dihydroartemisinin-piperazine for the prevention of malaria in Ugandan children	not seasonal
Sylla 2016	Immunological effect of seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) with sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (SP) and amodiaquine (AQ) in children under 10 years in the southeastern part of senegal	no outcomes
Tagbor 2015	The protective efficacy of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in an area of extended seasonal transmission in the ashanti region of Ghana: An individually randomized trial	link to included

Tarning 2018	Pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic properties of dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine in seasonal malaria chemoprevention in young children	no outcomes
Temperley 2008	Costs and cost-effectiveness of delivering intermittent preventive treatment for malaria through schools in western Kenya	not seasonal
Temperley 2008	Costs and cost-effectiveness of delivering intermittent preventive treatment through schools in western Kenya	not seasonal
Thomas 2017	Malaria prevention with nutrient supplementation in addition to seasonal chemoprevention in children aged 6-59 months in rural mali	intervention: SMC+nutrition
Tine 2011	Impact of combining intermittent preventive treatment with home management of malaria in children under 10 years, in a rural area of Senegal	intervention: < 3 cycles
Tine 2011	Impact of combining intermittent preventive treatment with home management of malaria in children less than 10 years in a rural area of Senegal: a cluster randomized trial	intervention: < 3 cycles
Tine 2013	Feasibility, safety and effectiveness of combining home based malaria management (HMM) and seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) in children less than ten years in Senegal: A clusterrandomized trial	link to included
Tine 2013	Acceptability by community health workers in Senegal of combining community case management of malaria and seasonal malaria chemoprevention	no outcomes
Tine 2014	Combining community case management of malarial and seasonal malaria chemoprevention for children less than 10 years in Senegal: Feasibility, impact on malaria and Anemia	link to included
Toure 2016	Failure of available malaria control interventions in dangassa, mali: Continuously high prevalence of plasmodium falciparum infection in a cohort of 1,400 individuals from 2012 to 2015	no control
Toure 2017	Age-specific changes in the incidence of uncomplicated plasmodium falciparum malaria: Seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) in an area with intense transmission: Dangassa, Mali	abstract only
VanHulle 2017	IMPLEMENTING SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION (SMC) IN THE CONTEXT OF EBOLA VIRUS DISEASE (EVD) IN GUINEA	no control
Wagman 2017	Observational evidence of a complimentary effect of combining next generation indoor residual spraying	link to included

	and seasonal malaria chemoprevention in the segou region of mali, 2014	
Ward 2014	Comparison of seasonal malaria chemoprevention coverage in northern Nigeria via door-to-door, health facility and retail sector delivery	no outcomes
Ward 2015	Impact of integrating the delivery of seasonal malaria chemoprevention with nutrition supplementation in northern Nigeria on health outcomes: A pragmatic intervention trial	intervention: SMC+nutrition
Ward 2019	Seasonal malaria chemoprevention packaged with malnutrition prevention in northern Nigeria: A pragmatic trial (SMAMP study) with nested case-control	intervention: SMC+nutrition
Wilson 2011	A systematic review and meta-analysis of the efficacy and safety of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in children (IPTc)	review
Yerbanga 2016	Assessment of malaria transmission from human to mosquitoes in seasonal malaria chemoprevention in the western region of Burkina Faso	no outcomes
York 2017	Seasonal malaria chemoprevention in the Sahel	no primary data
Zongo 2016	Dihydroartemisin-piperaquine for seasonal malaria chemoprevention	no control
Zongo 2017	DIHYDROARTEMISIN-PIPERAQUINE FOR SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION	no control
Zongo 2019	Optimizing delivery of seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) for children under five years of age: Very high coverage consistently achieved through door-to-door campaigns in Burkina Faso	no outcomes
Zuilkowski 2014	Early childhood malaria prevention and children's patterns of school leaving in the Gambia	no outcomes

References to studies

Included studies

Ambe 2020

Ambe J P, Balogun S T, Waziri M B, Nglass I N, Saddiq A. Impacts of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention on Malaria Burden among under Five-Year-Old Children in Borno State, Nigeria. 2020;2020:9372457-.

Cisse 2006

Cisse B, Sokhna C, Boulanger D, Milet J, Ba el H, Richardson K, et al. Seasonal intermittent preventive treatment with artesunate and sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine for prevention of malaria in Senegalese children: a randomised, placebo-controlled, double-blind trial. 2006;367(9511):659-67.

Cisse 2016

Cisse B, Ba E H, Sokhna C, N Diaye JL, Gomis J F, Dial Y, et al. Effectiveness of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention in Children under Ten Years of Age in Senegal: A Stepped-Wedge Cluster-Randomised Trial. 2016;13(11):e1002175-.

Dicko 2011

Dicko A, Diallo A I, Tembine I, Dicko Y, Dara N, Sidibe Y, et al. Intermittent preventive treatment of malaria provides substantial protection against malaria in children already protected by an insecticide-treated bednet in Mali: a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. 2011;8(2):e1000407-.

Dicko 2011a

Dicko A, Barry A, Dicko M, Diallo A I, Tembine I, Dicko Y, et al. Malaria morbidity in children in the year after they had received intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in Mali: a randomized control trial. 2011;6(8):e23390-.

Issiaka 2020

Issiaka D, Barry A, Traore T, Diarra B, Cook D, Keita M, et al. Impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention on hospital admissions and mortality in children under 5 years of age in Ouesselbouyou, Mali. 2020;19(1):103-.

Konate 2011

Konate A T, Yaro J B, Ouedraogo A Z, Diarra A, Gansane A, Soulama I, et al. Intermittent preventive treatment of malaria provides substantial protection against malaria in children already protected by an insecticide-treated bednet in Burkina Faso: a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. 2011;8(2):e1000408-.

Kweku 2008

Kweku M, Liu D, Adjuik M, Binka F, Seidu M, Greenwood B, et al. Seasonal intermittent preventive treatment for the prevention of anaemia and malaria in Ghanaian children: a randomized, placebo controlled trial. 2008;3(12):e4000-.

Ndiaye 2019

Ndiaye J L A, Ndiaye Y, Ba M S, Faye B, Ndiaye M, Seck A, et al. Seasonal malaria chemoprevention combined with community case management of malaria in children under 10 years of age, over 5 months, in south-east Senegal: A cluster-randomised trial. 2019;16(3):e1002762-.

Opoku 2016

Opoku E C, Olsen A, Browne E, Hodgson A, Awoonor-Williams J K, Yelifari L, et al. Impact of combined intermittent preventive treatment of malaria and helminths on anaemia, sustained attention, and recall in Northern Ghanaian schoolchildren. 2016;9:32197-.

Salissou 2017

Salissou I, Moustapha L M, Alkassoum I, Hadiza D, Ibrahim M L. Estimation of public health impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Niger. 2017;11(2):685-93.

Sesay 2011

Sesay S, Milligan P, Touray E, Sowe M, Webb E L, Greenwood B M, et al. A trial of intermittent preventive treatment and home-based management of malaria in a rural area of The Gambia. 2011;10:2-.

Tagbor 2011

Tagbor H, Cairns M, Nakwa E, Browne E, Sarkodie B, Counihan H, et al. The clinical impact of combining intermittent preventive treatment with home management of malaria in children aged below 5 years: cluster randomised trial. 2011;16(3):280-9.

Tagbor 2016

Tagbor H, Antwi G D, Acheampong P R, Bart Plange C, Chandramohan D, Cairns M. Seasonal malaria chemoprevention in an area of extended seasonal transmission in Ashanti, Ghana: an individually randomised clinical trial. 2016;21(2):224-35.

Thera 2018

Thera M A, Kone A K, Tangara B, Diarra E, Niare S, Dembele A, et al. School-aged children based seasonal malaria chemoprevention using artesunate-amodiaquine in Mali. 2018;3(2):96-105.

Tine 2014

Tine R C, Ndour C T, Faye B, Ndiaye M, Sylla K, Sow D, et al. Feasibility, safety and effectiveness of combining home based malaria management (HMM) and seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) in children less than ten years in Senegal: A cluster randomized trial. 2013;1):346-.

Wagman 2020

Wagman J, Cisse I, Kone D, Fomba S, Eckert E, Mihigo J, et al. Combining next-generation indoor residual spraying and drug-based malaria control strategies: observational evidence of a combined effect in Mali. 2020;19(1):293-.

Zongo 2015

Zongo I, Milligan P, Compaore Y D, Some A F, Greenwood B, Tarning J, et al. Randomized Noninferiority Trial of Dihydroartemisinin-Piperaquine Compared with Sulfadoxine-Pyrimethamine plus Amodiaquine for Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention in Burkina Faso. 2015;59(8):4387-96.

Excluded studies**Abiola 2015**

Abiola A W. Impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in the production of msp1 the ama1 antibodies in Senegal. 2015;93 (4 Supplement):99-.

Ahorlu 2009

Ahorlu C S, Koram K A, Seake-Kwawu A. Effectiveness of intermittent preventive treatment for children (IPTC) combined with timely treatment at home for malaria control. 2009;1):323-.

Ahorlu 2009a

Ahorlu C K, Koram K A, Seakey A K, Weiss M G. Effectiveness of combined intermittent preventive treatment for children and timely home treatment for malaria control. 2009;8:292-.

Ahorlu 2011

Ahorlu C K, Koram K A, Seake-Kwawu A, Weiss M G. Two-year evaluation of Intermittent Preventive Treatment for Children (IPTc) combined with timely home treatment for malaria control in Ghana. 2011;10:127-.

Aikins 2017

Aikins M, Nonvignon J, Aryeetey G C, Issah S, University of Ghana/School of Public Health Accra Ghana. COST-EFFECTIVENESS OF SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION IN UPPER WEST REGION OF GHANA. 2017;95:1pp.

Alexander 2007

Alexander N, Sutherland C, Roper C, Cisse B, Schellenberg D. Modelling the impact of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria on selection pressure for drug resistance. 2007;6:9-.

Angoran-Benie 2019

Angoran-Benie H, Jackou H, Yameni C. Community-based approach to reach malnourished infants from 6 months to 5 years during a seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) campaign in remote areas in Niger. 2019;101 (5 Supplement):519-.

Anne 2018

Anne M, Keita I M, Dieye K, Gueye A, Camara A Y, Sene D, et al. Strategy for improving the treatment of seasonal malaria chemoprevention among children from 3 to 120 months of age in goudomp health district, Senegal: A 3-day directly observed treatment initiative. 2018;99 (4 Supplement):122-.

Anne 2019

Anne M, Leye M M, Sene D, Dieye A K, Keita I M, Ndiaye Y. Seasonal malaria chimio prevention 2017 in the health district of goudomp Senegal costeffectiveness analysis of two treatment strategies for children aged 3-120 months. 2019;101 (5 Supplement):270-.

Anonymous 2016

Anonymous. Correction: safety of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention (SMC) with sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine plus amodiaquine when delivered to children under 10 years of age by district health services in senegal: results from a stepped-wedge cluster randomized trial (PLoS ONE (2016) 11: 10 (e0162563) DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0162563). 2016;11(12) (no pagination).

Anonymous 2016a

Anonymous. Corrigendum: Impact of combined intermittent preventive treatment of malaria and helminths on anaemia, sustained attention, and recall in Northern Ghanaian schoolchildren. 2016;9:33548-.

Ansah 2016

Ansah N A, Malm K, Chatio S T, Ansah P, Tampuulo S, Awuni D, et al. Evaluation of the impact of implementation of seasonal malaria chemoprevention on morbidity and mortality in young children: A qualitative study in Northern Ghana. 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):131-.

Antwi 2016

Antwi G D, Bates L A, King R, Mahama P R, Tagbor H, Cairns M, et al. Facilitators and Barriers to Uptake of an Extended Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention Programme in Ghana: A Qualitative Study of Caregivers and Community Health Workers. 2016;11(11):e0166951-.

Attaher 2016

Attaher O, Irfan Z, Cisse K B, Samassekou M B, Issiaka D, Coulibaly B, et al. Influence of seasonal malaria chemoprevention on markers of T cell exhaustion and immunoregulation. 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):298-9.

Attaher 2020

Attaher O, Zaidi I, Kwan J L, Issiaka D, Samassekou M B, Cisse K B, et al. Effect of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention on Immune Markers of Exhaustion and Regulation. 2020;221(1):138-45.

Ba 2014

Ba E K, Cisse B, Pitt C, Ndiaye J L, Ndiaye M, Gomis J F, et al. Extending the age range for seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC): Effectiveness of SMC in children under 10 years of age delivered through the district health service in Senegal. 2014;1):583-.

Ba 2018

Ba E H, Pitt C, Dial Y, Faye S L, Cairns M, Faye E, et al. Implementation, coverage and equity of large-scale door-to-door delivery of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention (SMC) to children under 10 in Senegal. 2018;8(1):5489-.

Barger 2009

Barger B, Maiga H, Traore O B, Tekete M, Tembine I, Dara A, et al. Intermittent preventive treatment using artemisinin-based combination therapy reduces malaria morbidity among school-aged children in Mali. 2009;14(7):784-91.

Barry 2016

Barry A, Issiaka D, Traore T, Diarra B, Kone D, Sagara I, et al. Comparison of three versus four rounds of seasonal malaria chemoprevention on the incidence of clinical malaria in mali. 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):6-7.

Barry 2018

Barry A, Issiaka D, Traore T, Mahamar A, Diarra B, Sagara I, et al. Optimal mode for delivery of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Ouelessebougou, Mali: A cluster randomized trial. 2018;13(3):e0193296-.

Beeson 2011

Beeson J G, Rogerson S J, Mueller I, Richards J S, Fowkes F J. Intermittent preventive treatment to reduce the burden of malaria in children: new evidence on integration and delivery. 2011;8(2):e1000410-.

Beshir 2016

Beshir K, Muwanguzi J, Doumagoum D, Gami J P, Zongo I, Ouedraogo J B, et al. Baseline frequencies of molecular markers of drug resistance before scaling-up access to seasonal malaria chemoprevention in seven countries across the sahel. 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):400-.

Beshir 2017

Beshir K, Ogboi S, Ceesay S, Diallo A, Ouedraogo J B, Zongo I, et al. Baseline molecular data before scaling-up of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in seven countries across the Sahel. 2017;97 (5 Supplement 1):486-.

Bicaba 2020

Bicaba A, Serme L, Chetaille G, Kombate G, Bila A, Haddad S. Longitudinal analysis of the capacities of community health workers mobilized for seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Burkina Faso. 2020;19(1):118-.

Bigira 2012

Bigira V I, Kapisi J, Kinara S, Mwangwa F, Osterbauer B, Okiring J, et al. Assessing the association between malaria chemoprevention and the nutritional status of a cohort of young african children. 2012;1):111-.

Bigira 2014

Bigira V, Kapisi J, Clark T D, Kinara S, Mwangwa F, Muhindo M K, et al. Protective efficacy and safety of three antimalarial regimens for the prevention of malaria in young Ugandan children: a randomized controlled trial. 2014;11(8):e1001689-.

Bisanzio 2019

Bisanzio D, Fofana A, Guilavogui T, Lama E K, Fitch E, Preston A, et al. The effectiveness of seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) in the operational programming context of Guinea. 2019;101 (5 Supplement):599-.

Bojang 2008

Bojang K, Akor F, Bittaye O, Conway D, Bottomley C, Milligan P, et al. A randomised trial to compare the safety, tolerability and efficacy of three drug combinations for intermittent preventive treatment in children. 2008;18.

Bojang 2009

Bojang K A, Sesay S, Sowe M, Conway D, Milligan P, Greenwood B. A Study of intermittent preventive treatment and home based management of malaria in a rural area of The Gambia. 2009;1):145-.

Bojang 2010

Bojang K, Akor F, Bittaye O, Conway D, Bottomley C, Milligan P, et al. A randomised trial to compare the safety, tolerability and efficacy of three drug combinations for intermittent preventive treatment in children. 2010;5(6):e11225-.

Bojang 2011

Bojang K A, Akor F, Conteh L, Webb E, Bittaye O, Conway D J, et al. Two strategies for the delivery of IPTc in an area of seasonal malaria transmission in the Gambia: a randomised controlled trial. 2011;8(2):e1000409-.

Bonkougou 2018

Bonkougou M, Badolo O, Nebie S, Tiendrebeogo J, Dodo M, Ouedraogo T, et al. Seasonal malaria chemoprevention, an effective intervention for reducing malaria morbidity and mortality. 2018;99 (4 Supplement):663-.

Bonkougou 2019

Bonkougou M, Sawadogo Y, Nebie S, Ouedraogo T, Savadogo Y, Brieger W, et al. Using seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) to screen for acute malnutrition. 2019;101 (5 Supplement):471-2.

Boulanger 2010

Boulanger D, Sarr J B, Fillol F, Sokhna C, Cisse B, Schacht A M, et al. Immunological consequences of intermittent preventive treatment against malaria in Senegalese preschool children. 2010;9:363-.

Brune 2017

Brune R, Thierry F, Arsene R. Seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Ankililoaka, Madagascar. 2017;97 (5 Supplement 1):503-4.

Cairns 2010

Cairns M, Cisse B, Sokhna C, Cames C, Simondon K, Ba E H, et al. Amodiaquine dosage and tolerability for intermittent preventive treatment to prevent malaria in children. 2010;54(3):1265-74.

Cairns 2012

Cairns M, Roca-Feltrer A, Garske T, Wilson A L, Diallo D, Milligan P J, et al. Estimating the potential public health impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in African children. 2012;3:881-.

Cairns 2015

Cairns M, Walker P G T. Randomised controlled trial: Monthly malaria chemoprevention shows potential in an area of very high, perennial malaria transmission. 2015;20(3):110-.

Cairns 2015a

Cairns M, Cheung Y B, Xu Y, Asante K P, Owusu-Agyei S, Diallo D, et al. Analysis of Preventive Interventions for Malaria: Exploring Partial and Complete Protection and Total and Primary Intervention Effects. 2015;181(12):1008-17.

Cairns 2016

Cairns M, Walker P G, Griffn J T, Milligan P J, Ghani A C. Optimizing seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) in africa: Estimating the impact of increasing the number of smc cycles on the number of children protected, the malaria burden and cost-effectiveness. 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):399-.

Cairns 2017

Cairns M, Ceesay S, Zongo I, Sagara I, Kessely H, Ogboi S, et al. Monitoring the protective efficacy of seasonal malaria chemoprevention using case-control studies: Methodology and results from 5 countries. 2017;97 (5 Supplement 1):541-.

Cairns 2019

Cairns M, Sagara I, Zongo I, Kuepfer I, Nikiema F, Yerbanga S, et al. Effectiveness of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in areas of intense, seasonal malaria transmission: Secondary analysis of data from a household-randomized clinical trial in burkina faso and mali. 2019;101 (5 Supplement):312-.

Cairns 2019a

Cairns M, Phiri M, Zongo I, Sagara I, Kuepfer I, Nikiema F, et al. The duration of protection from azithromycin against malaria, pneumonia and gastroenteritis when given alongside seasonal malaria chemoprevention: Secondary analysis of data from a clinical trial in Hounde, Burkina Faso and Bougouni, Mali. 2019;101 (5 Supplement):598-9.

Cairns 2020

Cairns M E, Sagara I, Zongo I, Kuepfer I, Thera I, Nikiema F, et al. Evaluation of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in two areas of intense seasonal malaria transmission: Secondary analysis of a household-randomised, placebo-controlled trial in Hounde District, Burkina Faso and Bougouni District, Mali. 2020;17(8):e1003214-.

CairnsMatthew, 2015

CairnsMatthew, Walker Patrick G T. Monthly malaria chemoprevention shows potential in an area of very high, perennial malaria transmission. 2015;20(3):110.

Camara 2018

Camara A Y, Drame D, Hann M, Diarra B, Diedhiou K, Badou G. Perception of the mothers and the child minders of the region of sedhiou on the seasonal malaria chemoprevention in 2017: Are the absences and the diseases of the children - No cases of disguised refusals? 2018;99 (4 Supplement):124-.

Ceesay 2016

Ceesay S, Hubbard E, Bojang K, Kandeh B, Kolley O, Jah H, et al. Implementation of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in the gambia. 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):576-.

Ceesay 2017

Ceesay S, Hubbard E, Bojang K, Kandeh B, Kolley O et al, Mrc Laboratories Fajara Gambia. IMPLEMENTATION OF SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION IN THE GAMBIA. 2017;95:1pp.

Chandramohan 2019

Chandramohan D, Dicko A, Zongo I, Sagara I, Cairns M, Kuepfer I, et al. Effect of Adding Azithromycin to Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention. 2019;380(23):2197-206.

Chatio 2019

Chatio S, Ansah N A, Awuni D A, Oduro A, Ansah P O. Community acceptability of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention of morbidity and mortality in young children: A qualitative study in the Upper West Region of Ghana. 2019;14(5):e0216486-.

Cisse 2009

Cisse B, Cairns M, Faye E, N Diaye O, Faye B, Cames C, et al. Randomized trial of piperazine with sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine or dihydroartemisinin for malaria intermittent preventive treatment in children. 2009;4(9):e7164-.

Clarke 2008

Clarke S E, Jukes M C, Njagi J K, Khasakhala L, Cundill B, Otido J, et al. Effect of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria on health and education in schoolchildren: a cluster-randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. 2008;372(9633):127-38.

Clarke 2014

Clarke S E, Griffiths Y, Dicko Y, Bamadio M, Diarra S, Thera P, et al. Seasonal malaria chemoprevention and micronutrient supplementation in early childhood: Effect on asymptomatic parasitaemia, anemia and Cognition. 2014;1):8-.

Clarke 2015

Clarke S E, Sacko M, Roschnik N, Dicko Y, Diarra S, Thera P, et al. Seasonal malaria chemoprevention combined with micronutrient supplementation delivered through community preschools: Findings from a cluster randomized trial in Mali. 2015;1):25-6.

Clarke 2016

Clarke S E, Roschnik N, Sacko M, Diarra N H, Thera P, Diarra S, et al. Impact of micronutrient supplementation combined with malaria chemoprevention on malaria, anaemia and cognitive development in early childhood: Findings from a cluster randomized study in southern mali. 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):537-.

Clarke 2017

Clarke S E, Rouhani S, Diarra S, Saye R, Bamadio M, Jones R, et al. Impact of a malaria intervention package in schools on Plasmodium infection, anaemia and cognitive function in schoolchildren in Mali: a pragmatic cluster-randomised trial. 2017;2(2):e000182-.

Clarke 2017a

Clarke S E, Roschnik N, Sacko M, Diarra N H, Thera P et al, London School of Hygiene, et al. IMPACT OF MICRONUTRIENT SUPPLEMENTATION COMBINED WITH MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION ON MALARIA, ANAEMIA AND COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT IN EARLY CHILDHOOD: FINDINGS FROM A CLUSTER RANDOMIZED STUDY IN SOUTHERN MALI. 2017;95:1-1.

Coldiron 2016

Coldiron M E, Lasry E, Bouhenia M, Das D, Mathela R, Salumu L, et al. Safety and tolerability of dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine as intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in a refugee camp, adjumani, Uganda. 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):273-.

Coldiron 2017

Coldiron M E, Assao B, Koscalova A, Quere M, Langendorf C et al, Epicentre Paris France. PROTECTIVE EFFECTIVENESS OF SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION IN NIGER: A PROSPECTIVE CASECONTROL STUDY. 2017;97(5):421.

Coldiron 2017a

Coldiron M E, Lasry E, Bouhenia M, Das D, Okui P, Nyehangane D, et al. Intermittent preventive treatment for malaria among children in a refugee camp in Northern Uganda: lessons learned. 2017;16(1):218-.

Coldiron 2017b

Coldiron M E, Assao B, Koscalova A, Quere M, Langendorf C, Grais R F. Prevalence of parasitemia in an area receiving SMC. 2017;22:221-224.

Coldiron 2017c

Coldiron M E, Assao B, Koscalova A, Quere M, Langendorf C, Grais R F. Prevalence of parasitemia during two seasons in an area receiving seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) in Niger. 2017;97 (5 Supplement 1):313-.

Coldiron 2019

Coldiron M E, Assao B, Langendorf C, Sayinzoga-Makombe N, Ciglencecki I, de la Tour R, et al. Clinical diagnostic evaluation of HRP2 and pLDH-based rapid diagnostic tests for malaria in an area receiving seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Niger. 2019;18(1):443-.

Compaore 2011

Compaore Y D, Some F, Zongo I, Rouamba N, Ouedraogo J B. Efficacy of dihydroartemisinin plus piperaquin compared to amodiaquin plus sulfadoxin/pyrimethamin in seasonal IPT of malaria in children in a rural area of Bobo-Dioulasso (Burkina Faso). 2011;1):457-.

Compaore 2017

Compaore Y D, Zongo I, Cox S E, Nikiema F, Tinto H, Chandramohan D, et al. Association of malaria and anemia with malnutrition in children following a seasonal malaria chemoprevention program in a rural area of burkina faso. 2017;97 (5 Supplement 1):107-8.

Compaore 2017a

Compaore R, Yameogo M W E, Millogo T, Tougri H, Kouanda S. Evaluation of the implementation fidelity of the seasonal malaria chemoprevention intervention in Kaya health district, Burkina Faso. 2017;12(11):e0187460-.

Conteh 2010

Conteh L, Patouillard E, Kweku M, Legood R, Greenwood B, Chandramohan D. Cost effectiveness of seasonal intermittent preventive treatment using amodiaquine & artesunate or sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine in Ghanaian children. 2010;5(8):e12223-.

Danquah 2012

Danquah I, Dietz E, Zanger P, Reither K, Ziniel P, Bienzle U, et al. Reduced efficacy of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in malnourished children (Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy (2009) 53, 5 (1753-1759)). 2012;56(1):601-.

Diallo 2014

Diallo I, Diouf M L, Cisse M, Gueye A B, Ndiop M, Ba M. Pharmacovigilance during campaign of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Senegal, 2013. 2014;1):443-.

Diallo 2016

Diallo I, Diouf M L, Ndiaye J L, Ndiop M, Gueye A B, Mady B A. Active monitoring of pharmacovigilance at community level during the seasonal malaria chemoprevention campaign in the health district kolda senegal, 2015. 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):80-.

Diallo 2017

Diallo A, Loua K, Sagara I, Dicko A, Zongo I, Ouedraogo J B, et al. Monitoring seasonal malaria chemoprevention campaigns: lessons learned from coverage surveys in 7 countries. 2017;97 (5 Supplement 1):526-7.

Diallo 2018

Diallo I, Diouf M L, Cisse M, Gueye A B, Ndiop M, Sene D. Monitoring of pharmacovigilance during the seasonal malaria chemoprevention campaign in Senegal, 2013 to 2017. 2018;99 (4 Supplement):313-4.

Diarra 2015

Diarra Seybou, Ho Kathy, Dicko Yahia, Bamadio Modibo, Thera Philippe, Roschnik Natalie, et al. Qualitative Research to Inform the Implementation of Home Fortification with Nutrition Education with Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention through Early Childhood Development Centres for Children Aged 6-59 Months in Sikasso, Mali. 2015.

Diarra 2017

Diarra N H, Roschnik N, Clarke S, Sacko M, Dicko Y, Verhoef H, et al. Impact of micronutrient powders combined with malaria chemoprevention on anemia, malaria and cognitive development: A cluster-randomized study in malian children. 2017;71 (Supplement 2):370-1.

Diarra 2018

Diarra Y, Doumbia L, Kone O, Sangare L, Haidara D B B, Sanogo V, et al. Impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention on malaria transmission on two sites of therapeutic efficacy study in Mali. 2018;99 (4 Supplement):347-8.

Diarra 2019

Diarra Y, Doumbia L, Kone O, Keita I, Sangare L, Bouye H D, et al. Molecular studies of PfDHPS and PfDHFR during seasonal malaria chemoprevention at three study sites in Mali. 2019;101 (5 Supplement):473-.

Diawara 2017a

Diawara S, Diakite M, Sogoba N, Toure M, Sanogo D et al, Université des Sciences des techniques et des technologies de Bamako Bamako Mali. FAILURE OF AVAILABLE MALARIA CONTROL INTERVENTIONS IN DANGASSA, MALI: CONTINUOUSLY HIGH PREVALENCE OF PLASMODIUM FALCIPARUM INFECTION IN A COHORT OF 1,400 INDIVIDUALS FROM 2012 TO 2015. 2017;95:1-1.

Diawara 2019

Diawara S I, Eckert E, Mihigo J, Kamate B, Ouattara D, Kone D, et al. Impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention among children five to ten years of age in kita and bafoulabe districts, mali. 2019;101 (5 Supplement):314-.

Dicko 2008

Dicko A, Sagara I, Sissoko M S, Guindo O, Diallo A I, Kone M, et al. Impact of intermittent preventive treatment with sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine targeting the transmission season on the incidence of clinical malaria in children in Mali. 2008;7:123-.

Dicko 2016

Dicko A, Ouedraogo J B, Zongo I, Sagara I, Cairns M, Kuepfer I, et al. A trial of seasonal malaria chemoprevention plus azithromycin in African children. 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):481-.

Dieng 2019

Dieng C C, Gonzalez L, Pestana K, Dhikrullahi S B, Amoah L E, Afrane Y A, et al. Contrasting Asymptomatic and Drug Resistance Gene Prevalence of Plasmodium falciparum in Ghana: Implications on Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention. 2019;10(7):16-.

Ding 2020

Ding J, Coldiron M E, Assao B, Guindo O, Blessborn D, Winterberg M, et al. Adherence and Population Pharmacokinetic Properties of Amodiaquine When Used for Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention in African Children. 2020;107(5):1179-88.

Diouf 2015

Diouf M L, Ndiop M, Ba M, Twing J, Diallo I, Cisse M, et al. Seasonal malaria chemoprevention implementation in children from three to 120 months experience in the four southern regions in Senegal. 2015;93 (4 Supplement):506-.

Druetz 2017

Druetz T, Corneau-Tremblay N, Kouanda S, Millogo T, Ly A, Haddad S. Seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Burkina Faso protects children against malaria and anaemia under routine program implementation. 2017;22 (Supplement 1):59-60.

Druetz 2018

Druetz T, Corneau-Tremblay N, Millogo T, Kouanda S, Ly A, Bicaba A, et al. Impact Evaluation of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention under Routine Program Implementation: A Quasi-Experimental Study in Burkina Faso. 2018;98(2):524-33.

Druetz 2018a

Druetz T. Evaluation of direct and indirect effects of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Mali. 2018;8(1):8104-.

Esch 2018

Esch K, Hamilton M, Korenromp E, Lewinski J, Ratcliffe A. Estimating the health impact of a seasonal malaria chemoprevention intervention in mali in 2017: Modeling deaths averted, cases averted and disability adjusted life years (DALYS) averted. 2018;99 (4 Supplement):564-.

Esch 2019

Esch K, Hamilton M, Korenromp E, Lacroix E, Tetteh G, Thior M. Prospectively estimating the health impact of upcoming president's malaria initiative impact malaria project-supported seasonal malaria chemoprevention campaigns in 70 districts across niger, mali and Cameroon in 2019. 2019;101 (5 Supplement):305-.

Fabrice 2010

Fabrice S A. Prevalence and selection of Plasmodium falciparum drug resistance molecular markers under intermittent preventive therapy in Burkina Faso. 2010;1):142-.

Fabrice 2011

Fabrice S A, Zongo I, Rouamba N, Compaore Y D, Dokomajilar C, Rosenthal P J, et al. Plasmodium falciparum drug resistance molecular markers under intermittent preventive therapy with dihydroartemisinin-piperazine (DP) vs. amodiaquine-sulfadoxine/pyrimethamine (AQ-SP) in Burkina Faso. 2011;1):361-.

Geerligs 2003

Geerligs P D, Brabin B J, Eggelte T A. Analysis of the effects of malaria chemoprophylaxis in children on haematological responses, morbidity and mortality. 2003;81(3):205-16.

Grais 2018

Grais R F, Laminou I M, Woi-Messe L, Makarimi R, Bouriema S H, Langendorf C, et al. Molecular markers of resistance to amodiaquine plus sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine in an area with seasonal malaria chemoprevention in south central Niger. 2018;17(1):98-.

Gueye 2018

Gueye A B, Ndiop M, Diallo I, Gaye S, Diouf M L, Sene D. Decrease of malaria burden among children under five years and other age groups in SMC regions in Senegal. 2018;99 (4 Supplement):121-.

Guillebaud 2013

Guillebaud J, Mahamadou A, Zamanka H, Katzelma M, Arzika I, Ibrahim M L, et al. Epidemiology of malaria in an area of seasonal transmission in Niger and implications for the design of a seasonal malaria chemoprevention strategy. 2013;12:379-.

Hulle 2016

Hulle S V, Guilavogui T. Implementing seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) in the context of ebola virus disease (evd) in guinea. 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):211-.

Humphreys 2018

Humphreys G S, Flegg J, Van Eijk A. Spatiotemporal modelling of prevalence of plasmodium falciparum drug resistance mutations in the DHPS gene across Africa, 1990 - 2015. 2018;99 (4 Supplement):14-.

Issiaka 2015

Issiaka D, Barry A, Tounkara M, Traore T, Diarra I, Kone D, et al. Determining the optimal mode for delivery of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Mali. 2015;93 (4 Supplement):496-.

Issiaka 2017

Issiaka D, Gaudart J, Barry A, Traore T, Diarra B, Kone D, et al. Impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention on hospital admissions and mortality in children under 5 years in ouelessebouyou, Mali. 2017;97 (5 Supplement 1):551-.

Jagannathan 2016

Jagannathan P, Bowen K, Nankya F, McIntyre T I, Auma A, Wamala S, et al. Effective Antimalarial Chemoprevention in Childhood Enhances the Quality of CD4+ T Cells and Limits Their Production of Immunoregulatory Interleukin 10. 2016;214(2):329-38.

Jean 2012

Jean L A N, Ndiaye Y, Ba M S, Cisse B, Faye B, Ndiaye M, et al. Seasonal malaria chemoprevention and community case management for malaria in Southern senegal: A cluster-randomized trial. 2012;1):164-.

Kaly 2018

Kaly J S, Ndiaye Y, Faye A, Ba M. Knowledge, attitudes and practices of mothers caretakers of children aged 3 to 120 months on of seasonal malaria chemo prevention in bounkiling health district, South Senegal. 2018;99 (4 Supplement):349-.

Kamate 2017

Kamate B, Swedberg E A, Outtara D, Kone D, Mihigo J. Scaling up seasonal malaria chemoprevention in mali: Implementation challenges and lessons learned. 2017;97 (5 Supplement 1):526-.

Kamya 2020

Kamya M R, Kakuru A, Muhindo M, Arinaitwe E, Nankabirwa J I, Rek J, et al. The Impact of Control Interventions on Malaria Burden in Young Children in a Historically High-Transmission District of Uganda: A Pooled Analysis of Cohort Studies from 2007 to 2018. 2020;103(2):785-92.

Kana 2017

Kana M A, Cairns M, Lal S, Luqman A, Maikore I, Snell P, et al. Scaling-up of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in sokoto and zamfara states, Nigeria: Monitoring delivery and impact. 2017;97 (5 Supplement 1):531-.

Katile 2019

Katile A, Kamate B, Guindo C O, Kone M, Traore B, Dara J, et al. Malaria parasitemia incidence among different age groups in a stable transmission area of Mali receiving seasonal malaria chemoprevention. 2019;101 (5 Supplement):479-.

Kobbe 2011

Kobbe R, Hogan B, Adjei S, Klein P, Kreuels B, Loag W, et al. Follow-up survey of children who received sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine for intermittent preventive antimalarial treatment in infants. 2011;203(4):556-60.

Kombate 2019

Kombate G, Guiella G, Baya B, Serme L, Bila A, Haddad S, et al. Analysis of the quality of seasonal malaria chemoprevention provided by community health Workers in Boulsa health district, Burkina Faso. 2019;19(1):472-.

Konate 2019

Konate D, Diawara S I, Toure M, Diakite S A S, Guindo A, Diarra A, et al. Effect of seasonal malaria chemoprevention on malaria in children under 5 years: A cohort study in Dangassa, Mali. 2019;101 (5 Supplement):119-.

Konate 2020

Konate D, Diawara S I, Toure M, Diakite S A S, Guindo A, Traore K, et al. Effect of routine seasonal malaria chemoprevention on malaria trends in children under 5 years in Dangassa, Mali. 2020;19(1):137-.

Koscalova 2015

Koscalova A, Gignoux E, Ciglencecki I, Azman A, Sterk E, Quere M. Monitoring the protective effect and the effectiveness of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Niger. 2015;1):74-.

Koscalova 2017

Koscalova A, Temessadouno F, Gignoux E, Azman A, Querre M, Ciglencecki I, et al. Malaria incidence in the area of seasonal malaria chemoprevention. 2017;22 (Supplement 1):226-7.

Kpormegbe 2014

Kpormegbe S K, Ahorlu C K. The role of community participation in intermittent preventive treatment of childhood malaria in southeastern Ghana. 2014;48(2):58-65.

Kweku 2009

Kweku M, Webster J, Adjuik M, Abudey S, Greenwood B, Chandramohan D. Options for the delivery of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria to children: a community randomised trial. 2009;4(9):e7256-.

Kweku 2011

Kweku M A, Appiah E, Duah N O, Koram K A, Greenwood B, Chandramohan D. Assessment of the efficacy, tolerability and ease of administration of dihydroartemisinin plus piperazine and artesunate plus sulfamethoxypyrazine plus pyrimethamine compared with sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine for preventing malaria in Ghanaian children. 2011;1):139-.

Lasry 2015

Lasry E, Coldiron M, Koscalova A, Grandesso F, Milligan P, Angeles Lima M, et al. Seasonal malaria chemoprevention, three years of implementation. 2015;93 (4 Supplement):583-.

Le 2015

Le Menach A, Ward A, Guillot A, Greene S K, Graves J C, Maloney K, et al. Combining nutritional supplementation with seasonal malaria chemoprevention in nigeria decreases the odds of confirmed clinical malaria: Findings from a case-control study. 2015;93 (4 Supplement):398-.

Lo 2011

Lo A C. Impact of seasonal intermittent preventive treatment in children: Molecular markers of resistance in three health districts in Senegal. 2011;1):202-.

Lo 2012

Lo A C, Faye B, Abiola A K, Ndiaye M, Tine R C, Cisse B, et al. Prevalence of mutation of pfprt after the use of amodiaquine in intermittent preventive treatment in children (IPTC) in Senegal. 2012;1):104-.

Lo 2013

Lo A C, Faye B, Ba el H, Cisse B, Tine R, Abiola A, et al. Prevalence of molecular markers of drug resistance in an area of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in children in Senegal. 2013;12:137-.

Mahamar 2016

Mahamar A, Cisse K B, Diarra K, Soumare H, Issiaka D, Traore T, et al. Seasonal malaria chemoprevention is associated with a reduction in seropositivity to blood-stage antigens. 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):299-.

Mahamar 2017

Mahamar A, Issiaka D, Barry A, Attaher O, Dembele A B, Traore T, et al. Effect of seasonal malaria chemoprevention on the acquisition of antibodies to Plasmodium falciparum antigens in Ouelessebougou, Mali. 2017;16(1):289-.

Mahamar 2019

Mahamar A, Sumner K, Levitt B, Freedman B, Traore A, Barry A, et al. Long-term effect of seasonal malaria chemoprevention with amodiaquine plus sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine on molecular markers of resistance in ouelessebougou, Mali. 2019;101 (5 Supplement):83-.

Mahamar 2019a

Mahamar A, Issiaka D, Youssouf A, Mohamed Niambele S, Soumare H M, Attaher O, et al. Effect of four years of seasonal malaria chemoprevention on the acquisition of antibodies to plasmodium falciparum antigens in ouelessebougou, Mali. 2019;101 (5 Supplement):519-.

Maiga 2014

Maiga H, Barger B, Sagara I, Doumbo O, Djimde A. School performance after intermittent preventive treatment using artemisinin-based combination. 2014;1):277-.

Maiga 2016

Maiga H, Lasry E, Diarra M, Sagara I, Bamadio A, Traore A, et al. Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention with Sulphadoxine-Pyrimethamine and Amodiaquine Selects Pfdhfr-dhps Quintuple Mutant Genotype in Mali. 2016;11(9):e0162718-.

Maiga 2018

Maiga H I, Bamadio A, Traore A, Diallo N, Diarra M, Sagara I, et al. Selection of seven-mutation Pfcrt-Pfmdr1 genotype after scaling seasonal malaria chemoprevention with sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine and amodiaquine in Mali. 2018;99 (4 Supplement):82-.

Maiteki 2015

Maiteki C, Gonahasa S, Kigozi S P, Drakeley C, Rehman A M, Chandler C I, et al. School-based treatment with act to reduce transmission' (start-IPT): Evaluation of the community impact of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in Ugandan children. 2015;93 (4 Supplement):84-.

Maiteki-Sebuguzi 2017

Maiteki-Sebuguzi C, Rehman A M, Kigozi S P, Gonahasa S, Lindsay S et al, Infectious Diseases Research Collaboration Kampala Uganda. EVALUATING THE COMMUNITY-LEVEL IMPACT OF INTERMITTENT PREVENTIVE TREATMENT OF SCHOOLCHILDREN FOR MALARIA IN JINJA, UGANDA: A CLUSTER-RANDOMIZED TRIAL. 2017;95:1-1.

Matangila 2015

Matangila J R, Mitashi P, Inocencio da Luz R A, Lutumba P T, Van Geertruyden J P. Efficacy and safety of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in schoolchildren: a systematic review. 2015;14:450-.

Matangila 2015a

Matangila J, Da Luz R I, Lutumba P, Van Geertruyden J P. Efficacy and safety of intermittent preventive treatment with sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (SP) and SP-piperaquine in schoolchildren in Kinshasa, The Democratic Republic of the Congo (RDC). 2015;1):179-80.

Matangila 2017

Matangila J R, Fraeyman J, Kambulu M M, Mpanya A, da Luz R I, Lutumba P, et al. The perception of parents and teachers about intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in school children in a semi-rural area of Kinshasa, in the Democratic Republic of Congo. 2017;16(1):19-.

Matangila 2017a

Matangila J R, Doua J Y, Mitashi P, da Luz R I, Lutumba P, Van Geertruyden J P. Efficacy and safety of intermittent preventive treatment in schoolchildren with sulfadoxine/pyrimethamine (SP) and SP plus piperaquine in Democratic Republic of the Congo: a randomised controlled trial. 2017;49(3):339-47.

Moroso 2017

Moroso D. Transforming the malaria landscape: Results from a threeyear implementation research project expanding access to seasonal malaria chemoprevention in seven Sahelian countries (ACCESS-SMC). 2017;22 (Supplement 1):363-.

Muhindo 2017

Muhindo M K, Kakuru A, Awori P, Natureeba P, Opira B, Amailuk M, et al. Intermittent preventive treatment with dihydroartemisinin-piperazine in young Ugandan children in the setting of indoor residual spraying of insecticide. 2017;97 (5 Supplement 1):291-.

N 2016

N Diaye JL, Cisse B, Ba E H, Gomis J F, Ndour C T, Molez J F, et al. Safety of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention (SMC) with Sulfadoxine-Pyrimethamine plus Amodiaquine when Delivered to Children under 10 Years of Age by District Health Services in Senegal: Results from a Stepped-Wedge Cluster Randomized Trial. 2016;11(10):e0162563-.

Namirimu 2013

Namirimu F N, Jagannathan P, Eccles-James I, Bowen K, Wamala S, Naluwu K, et al. Impact of chemoprevention on the development of t cell responses to malaria. 2013;1):59-.

Nankabirwa 2010

Nankabirwa J, Cundill B, Clarke S, Kabatereine N, Rosenthal P J, Dorsey G, et al. Efficacy, safety, and tolerability of three regimens for prevention of malaria: a randomized, placebo-controlled trial in Ugandan schoolchildren. 2010;5(10):e13438-.

Nankabirwa 2014

Nankabirwa J I, Wandera B, Amuge P, Kiwanuka N, Dorsey G, Rosenthal P J, et al. Impact of intermittent preventive treatment with dihydroartemisinin-piperazine on malaria in Ugandan schoolchildren: a randomized, placebo-controlled trial. 2014;58(10):1404-12.

National 2020

National Institute for Medical Research Tanzania, National Malaria Control Program Tanzania. Evaluation of the Implementation and Effectiveness of Intermittent Preventive Treatment for Malaria Using Dihydroartemisinin-piperazine on Reducing Malaria Burden in School Aged Children in Tanzania. 2020.

Nayiga 2015

Nayiga S, Nabirye C, Staedke S, Chandler C I R. Lessons for integrating intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in school systems in low income settings: Experiences from Uganda. 2015;93 (4 Supplement):108-.

Nct 2005

Nct. Study of the Impact of Intermittent Preventive Treatment in Schools on Malaria, Anaemia and Education. 2005.

Nct 2014

Nct. A Trial of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention Plus Azithromycin in African Children. 2014.

Nct 2017

Nct. Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention With or Without Lipid-based Nutrient Supplement in Children Aged 6-59 Months in Mali. 2017.

Nct 2019

Nct. Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention With Dihydroartemisin Piperaquin vs. Sulfadoxine-pyrimethamin+Amodiaquin. 2019.

Ndiaye 2011

Ndiaye M, Pitt C, Conteh L, Ba E H, Camara P, Gaye O, et al. Costing a large-scale implementation of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in children delivered through community health workers in Senegal. 2011;1):111-.

Ndiaye 2011a

Ndiaye M, Faye B, Alifrangis M, Tine R, Ndiaye J L, Dieng Y, et al. Impact of intermittent preventive treatment in children (IPTC) on Plasmodium falciparum infections complexity: Resistance markers and kinetic of antibodies against P. falciparum in Senegal. 2011;1):53-4.

Ndiaye 2011b

Ndiaye M, Alifrangis M, Faye B, Hallett R, Tine R, Ndiaye J L, et al. Monitoring of drug resistance after intermittent preventive treatment for infants and children (IPTi/C) in Senegal. 2011;1):355-.

Ndiaye 2011c

Ndiaye J L A, Cisse B, Ba E H, Gomis J F, Molez J F, Fall F B, et al. Safety of seasonal intermittent preventive treatment against malaria with sulfadoxine pyrimethamine + amodiaquine when delivered to children under ten years of age by district health staff in Senegal. 2011;1):269-70.

Ndiaye 2012

Ndiaye M, Pitt C, Conteh L, Ba E H, Sy O, Camara P I, et al. Costing a large-scale implementation of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in children delivered through community health workers in senegal. 2012;1):406-.

Ndiaye 2013

Ndiaye M, Tine R, Faye B, Ndiaye J L, Diouf I, Lo A C, et al. Selection of antimalarial drug resistance after intermittent preventive treatment of infants and children (IPTi/c) in Senegal. 2013;336(5-6):295-300.

Ndiaye 2013a

Ndiaye J L A, Ndiaye Y, Ba M S, Faye B, Ndiaye D, Tine R C, et al. Seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Senegal: From research to policy. 2013;1):200-.

Ndiaye 2013b

Ndiaye J L, Ba M S, Ndiaye Y, Ndiaye M, Cisse B, Faye B, et al. Evaluation of the tolerance of sulfadoxinepyrimethamine + amodiaquine combination in seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) combined with home based management (HMM) in children under 10 years in Senegal. 2013;1):168-.

Ndiaye 2014

Ndiaye M, Sylla K, Tine R C, Faye B, Ndiaye J L, Lo A C, et al. Potential impact of intermittent preventive treatment (IPT) on the acquisition of antibodies to malaria antigens GLURP-R0 and AMA-1 in senegalese children. 2014;1):118-.

Ndiaye 2015

Ndiaye M, Sylla K, Sow D, Tine R, Faye B, Ndiaye J L, et al. Potential Impact of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention on the Acquisition of Antibodies Against Glutamate-Rich Protein and Apical Membrane Antigen 1 in Children Living in Southern Senegal. 2015;93(4):798-800.

Ndiaye 2015a

Ndiaye J L A, Faye B, Ndiaye M, Ndiaye D, Ndiop M, Manga I A, et al. Evaluation of the impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention administered by mass campaign in Southern Senegal. 2015;93 (4 Supplement):458-.

Ndiaye 2016

Ndiaye Y, Ndiaye J L, Dieye A K, Aw I, Mbaye A, Gaye O, et al. Trends of high reduction of malaria cases in sedhiou district following seasonal malaria chemoprevention first campaign: Lessons learned. 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):469-70.

Ndiaye 2016a

Ndiaye J L, Sylla K, Tine R C, Sow D, Ndiaye M et al, Sylla K et al, et al. IMMUNOLOGICAL EFFECT OF SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION (SMC) WITH SULFADOXINEPYRIMETHAMINE (SP) AND AMODIAQUINE (AQ) IN CHILDREN UNDER 10 YEARS IN THE SOUTHEASTERN PART OF SENEGAL. 2016;95:115.

Ndiaye 2016b

Ndiaye J L A, Manga I A, Ndiop M, Ndiaye Y, Faye B, Ndiaye M, et al. Impact evaluation after three years of seasonal malaria chemoprevention implementation by mass campaigns in southern senegal. 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):469-.

Ndiaye 2017

Ndiaye Y, Ndiaye J L, Dieye A K, Aw I, Mbaye A et al, Ministry of Health, et al. TRENDS OF HIGH REDUCTION OF MALARIA CASES IN SEDHIOU DISTRICT FOLLOWING SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION FIRST CAMPAIGN: LESSONS LEARNED . 2017;95:1-1.

Ndiaye 2017a

Ndiaye J L A, Manga I A, Tairou F, Ndiop M, Diallo I, Tine R, et al. Impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention after 3 years at scale in Southern Senegal. 2017;97 (5 Supplement 1):134-.

Ndiaye 2017b

Ndiaye Y, Faye B, Ndiaye J L A, Manga I A, Ndiop M et al, Service de Parasitologie Dakar Senegal. IMPACT EVALUATION AFTER THREE YEARS OF SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION IMPLEMENTATION BY MASS CAMPAIGNS IN SOUTHERN SENEGAL. 2017;95:1-1.

Ndiaye 2018

Ndiaye J A, Diallo I, N Diaye Y, Kouevidjin E, Aw I, Tairou F, et al. Evaluation of Two Strategies for Community-Based Safety Monitoring during Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention Campaigns in Senegal, Compared with the National Spontaneous Reporting System. 2018;32(3):189-200.

Ndiop 2015

Ndiop M, Diallo I, Thwing J, Gaye S, Gueye A B, Cisse M, et al. Tracking the impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention on morbidity and mortality of children in senegal through the routine health information system. 2015;93 (4 Supplement):93-.

Ndiop 2017

Ndiop M, Thwing J I, Diouf M L, Cisse M, Gueye A B, Diallo I, et al. Has seasonal malaria chemoprevention decreased the malaria burden among children under five years in Senegal? 2017;97 (5 Supplement 1):313-.

Nonvignon 2016

Nonvignon J, Aryeetey G C, Issah S, Ansah P, Malm K L, Ofosu W, et al. Cost-effectiveness of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in upper west region of Ghana. 2016;15:367-.

Noor 2015

Noor A M, Kibuchi E, Mitto B, Coulibaly D, Doumbo O K, Snow R W. Sub-National Targeting of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention in the Sahelian Countries of the Nouakchott Initiative. 2015;10(8):e0136919-.

Ntab 2007

Ntab B, Cisse B, Boulanger D, Sokhna C, Targett G, Lines J, et al. Impact of intermittent preventive anti-malarial treatment on the growth and nutritional status of preschool children in rural Senegal (west Africa). 2007;77(3):411-7.

Obiero 2019

Obiero J M, Cairns M, Jain A, Taghavian O, Sy A, Nakajima R, et al. The effect of adding azithromycin to the antimalarials (sulphadoxine/pyrimethamine and amodiaquine) used for seasonal malaria chemoprevention on the immune response to plasmodium falciparum. 2019;101 (5 Supplement):302-.

Okuneye 2019

Okuneye K O, Gerardin J. Using models to inform implementation policies of seasonal malaria chemoprevention. 2019;101 (5 Supplement):125-6.

Oresanya 2019

Oresanya O B, Ahmadu A, Adesoro O, Maranda L, Morosso D, Maxwell K. An assessment of quality of delivery of seasonal malaria chemoprevention using low literate community health workers in nigeria. 2019;101 (5 Supplement):119-20.

Ouedraogo 2016

Ouedraogo J B, Zongo I, Yerbanga R S, Some F A, Snell P, Cairns M, et al. Effective scaling-up of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in burkina faso. 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):267-.

Ouedraogo 2016a

Ouedraogo A L, Eckhoff P A, Wenger E A. Impact of seasonal malaria chemoprophylaxis in a high and seasonal malaria transmission setting in burkina faso. 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):306-.

Ouedraogo 2017

Ouedraogo J B, Zongo I, Yerbanga R S, SomÃ© F A, Snell P et al, Institut de Recherche en Sciences de la SantÃ© Bobo-Dioulasso Burkina Faso. EFFECTIVE SCALING-UP OF SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION IN BURKINA FASO. 2017;95:1pp.

Ouedraogo 2017a

Ouedraogo A L, Gerardin J, Yanogo P, Zongo A, Savadogo Y, Eckhoff P A, et al. Understanding and optimizing operational seasonal malaria chemoprevention through data analysis and modeling: The example of Burkina Faso. 2017;97 (5 Supplement 1):486-.

Pactr 2013

Pactr. An integrated malaria control strategy including community case management and Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention in Senegal. 2013.

Pactr 2014

Pactr. Randomized open-label trial to evaluate the efficacy of artesunate-amodiaquin for seasonal malaria chemoprevention in suburban school of Bamako, Sirak. 2014.

Patouillard 2011

Patouillard E, Conteh L, Webster J, Kweku M, Chandramohan D, Greenwood B. Coverage, adherence and costs of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in children employing different delivery strategies in Jasikan, Ghana. 2011;6(11):e24871-.

Pitt 2012

Pitt C, Diawara H, Ouedraogo D J, Diarra S, Kabore H, Kouela K, et al. Intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in children: a qualitative study of community perceptions and recommendations in Burkina Faso and Mali. 2012;7(3):e32900-.

Pitt 2015

Pitt C, Ndiaye M, Conteh L, Sy O, Ba E H, Cisse B, et al. Delivering seasonal malaria chemoprevention to children under ten at scale in central Senegal: Costs and cost determinants. 2015;93 (4 Supplement):412-3.

Pitt 2017

Pitt C, Ndiaye M, Conteh L, Sy O, Hadj Ba E, Cisse B, et al. Large-scale delivery of seasonal malaria chemoprevention to children under 10 in Senegal: an economic analysis. 2017;32(9):1256-66.

Rehman 2019

Rehman A M, Maiteki-Sebuguzi C, Gonahasa S, Okiring J, Kigozi S P, Chandler C I R, et al. Intermittent preventive treatment of malaria delivered to primary schoolchildren provided effective individual protection in Jinja, Uganda: secondary outcomes of a cluster-randomized trial (START-IPT). 2019;18(1):318-.

Roger 2011

Roger T, Ndour C T, Faye B, Ndiaye J L, Magnussen P, Bassene C, et al. Impact of combining intermittent preventive treatment with home management of malaria in children under ten years, in a rural area of Senegal. 2011;1):270-.

Rohner 2010

Rohner F, Zimmermann M B, Amon R J, Vounatsou P, Tschannen A B, N'Goran E K, et al. In a randomized controlled trial of iron fortification, anthelmintic treatment, and intermittent preventive treatment of malaria for anemia control in Ivorian children, only anthelmintic treatment shows modest benefit. 2010;140(3):635-41.

Sagara 2016

Sagara I, Maiga H, Diawara F, Kaya M, Traore S, Dembele A, et al. Coverage of seasonal malaria chemoprevention delivered by mobile teams at fixed points in 14 districts in mali, through Access-Smc. 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):519-.

Sagara 2017

Sagara I, Maiga H, Kaya M, Traore S, Dembele A, Goro S, et al. Seasonal malaria chemoprevention scaling up and its impact assessment in Mali. 2017;97 (5 Supplement 1):531-.

Sagara 2017a

Sagara I, Maiga H, Diawara F, Kaya M, Traore S et al, Mrtc Bamako Mali. COVERAGE OF SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION DELIVERED BY MOBILE TEAMS AT FIXED POINTS IN 14 DISTRICTS IN MALI, THROUGH ACCESS-SMC. 2017;95:1-1.

Sagara 2017b

Sagara I, Chandramohan D, Dicko A, Ouedraogo J B, Zongo I et al, London School of Hygiene, et al. A TRIAL OF SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION PLUS AZITHROMYCIN IN AFRICAN CHILDREN. 2017;95:1-1.

Sagara 2018

Sagara I, Maiga H, Kaya M, Traore S, Goro S, Traore M, et al. Seasonal malaria chemoprevention scaling up in Mali: Coverage and impact on malaria burden and markers of the resistance of plasmodium falciparum to sulfadoxine pyrimethamine and amodiaquine. 2018;99 (4 Supplement):350-.

Salam 2014

Salam Rehana A, Das Jai K, Lassi Zohra S, Bhutta Zulfiqar A. Impact of community-based interventions for the prevention and control of malaria on intervention coverage and health outcomes for the prevention and control of malaria. 2014;3:25.

Salissou 2016

Salissou I, Moustapha L M, Yerima B, Alkassoum I, Hadiza D, Ibrahim M L. Perception of the seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Niger. 2016;10(6):2710-5.

Salissou 2016a

Salissou Issa, Mahaman Moustapha Lamine, Yerima Bako, Alkassoum Ibrahim, Hadiza Djakou, Ibrahim Maman Laminou. Perception de la chimioprÃ©vention du paludisme saisonnier au Niger. 2016;10:2710-5.

Sangare 2019

Sangare L, Kone O, Diarra Y, Doumbia L, Bouye H D, Sanogo V, et al. Seasonal malaria chemoprevention and compliance during four monthly treatments with sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine and amodiaquine at 3 study sites in Mali. 2019;101 (5 Supplement):273-.

Saye 2015

Saye R, Sacko M, Diarra S, Bamadio M, Dicko Y, Jones R, et al. Malaria chemoprevention, undernutrition and anaemia in children: Findings from three randomized intervention trials in Southern Mali. 2015;1):78-9.

Shehu 2017

Shehu U L. Malaria preventive practices and acceptability of seasonal malaria chemoprevention among caregivers of under five children in rural and urban communities of Kano, Nigeria, 2017. 2017;97 (5 Supplement 1):133-.

Sokhna 2008

Sokhna C, Cisse B, Ba el H, Milligan P, Hallett R, Sutherland C, et al. A trial of the efficacy, safety and impact on drug resistance of four drug regimens for seasonal intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in Senegalese children. 2008;3(1):e1471-.

Some 2014

Some A F, Zongo I, Compaore Y D, Sakande S, Nosten F, Ouedraogo J B, et al. Selection of drug resistance-mediating Plasmodium falciparum genetic polymorphisms by seasonal malaria chemoprevention in Burkina Faso. 2014;58(7):3660-5.

Soumare 2017

Soumare H, Issiaka D, Mahamar A, Ciosse K B, Diarra K et al, University of Science Techniques, et al. SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION IS ASSOCIATED WITH A REDUCTION IN SEROPOSITIVITY TO BLOOD-STAGE ANTIGENS. 2017;95:1-1.

Staedke 2018

Staedke S G, Maiteki-Sebuguzi C, Rehman A M, Kigozi S P, Gonahasa S, Okiring J, et al. Assessment of community-level effects of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in schoolchildren in Jinja, Uganda (START-IPT trial): a cluster-randomised trial. 2018;6(6):e668-79.

Strachan 2016

Strachan C E, Kana M, Martin S, Dada J, Wandera N, Marasciulo M, et al. The use of formative research to inform the design of a seasonal malaria chemoprevention intervention in northern Nigeria. 2016;15:474-.

Sundell 2015

Sundell K, Jagannathan P, Huang L, Bigira V, Kapisi J, Kakuru M M, et al. Variable piperazine exposure significantly impacts protective efficacy of monthly dihydroartemisinin-piperazine for the prevention of malaria in Ugandan children. 2015;14:368-.

Sylla 2016

Sylla K, Tine R C, Sow D, Ndiaye M, Ndiaye J L, Ndiaye D, et al. Immunological effect of seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) with sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (SP) and amodiaquine (AQ) in children under 10 years in the southeastern part of senegal. 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):115-.

Tagbor 2015

Tagbor H, Antwi G, Acheampong P R, Chandramohan D, Cairns M. The protective efficacy of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in an area of extended seasonal transmission in the ashanti region of Ghana: An individually randomized trial. 2015;93 (4 Supplement):243-4.

Tarning 2018

Tarning J, Chotsiri P, Zongo I, Milligan P, Compaore D, Some F, et al. Pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic properties of dihydroartemisinin-piperazine in seasonal malaria chemoprevention in young children. 2018;99 (4 Supplement):25-.

Temperley 2008

Temperley M, Mueller D H, Njagi J K, Akhwale W, Clarke S E, Jukes M C H, et al. Costs and cost-effectiveness of delivering intermittent preventive treatment for malaria through schools in western Kenya. 2008;7(196).

Temperley 2008a

Temperley M, Mueller D H, Njagi J K, Akhwale W, Clarke S E, Jukes M C, et al. Costs and cost-effectiveness of delivering intermittent preventive treatment through schools in western Kenya. 2008;7:196-.

Thomas 2017

Thomas A, Doutchi M, Issaley A, Kanta I, Daures M, Ouattara A, et al. Malaria prevention with nutrient supplementation in addition to seasonal chemoprevention in children aged 6-59 months in rural mali. 2017;97 (5 Supplement 1):87-.

Tine 2011

Tine R C, Ndour C T, Faye B, Ndiaye J L, Magnussen P, Bygbjer C, et al. Impact of combining intermittent preventive treatment with home management of malaria in children under 10 years, in a rural area of Senegal. 2011;1):101-2.

Tine 2011a

Tine R C, Faye B, Ndour C T, Ndiaye J L, Ndiaye M, Bassene C, et al. Impact of combining intermittent preventive treatment with home management of malaria in children less than 10 years in a rural area of Senegal: a cluster randomized trial. 2011;10:358-.

Tine 2013

Tine R C, Ndiaye P, Ndour C T, Faye B, Ndiaye J L, Sylla K, et al. Acceptability by community health workers in Senegal of combining community case management of malaria and seasonal malaria chemoprevention. 2013;12:467-.

Tine 2014

Tine R C, Ndour C T, Faye B, Cairns M, Sylla K, Ndiaye M, et al. Feasibility, safety and effectiveness of combining home based malaria management and seasonal malaria chemoprevention in children less than 10 years in Senegal: a cluster-randomised trial. 2014;108(1):13-21.

Tine 2014a

Tine R C, Faye B, Ndour C T, Cisse B, Cairns M, Ndiaye M, et al. Combining community case management of malarial and seasonal malaria chemoprevention for children less than 10 years in Senegal: Feasibility, impact on malaria and Anemia. 2014;1):75-.

Toure 2016

Toure M, Sanogo D, Diawara S, Diakite M, Sogoba N, Krogstad D, et al. Failure of available malaria control interventions in dangassa, mali: Continuously high prevalence of plasmodium falciparum infection in a cohort of 1,400 individuals from 2012 to 2015. 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):293-4.

Toure 2017

Toure M B, Sonogo D D, Keita M, Diarra A, Keita A S, Konate D D, et al. Age-specific changes in the incidence of uncomplicated plasmodium falciparum malaria: Seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) in an area with intense transmission: Dangassa, Mali. 2017;97 (5 Supplement 1):506-.

Van Hulle 2017

Van Hulle S, Guilavogui T, Catholic Relief Services U S A. IMPLEMENTING SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION (SMC) IN THE CONTEXT OF EBOLA VIRUS DISEASE (EVD) IN GUINEA. 2017;95:1-1.

Wagman 2017

Wagman J, Gogue C, Tynuv K, Mihigo J, Diallo D, Bankineza E, et al. Observational evidence of a complimentary effect of combining next generation indoor residual

spraying and seasonal malaria chemoprevention in the segou region of mali, 2014. 2017;97 (5 Supplement 1):540-1.

Ward 2014

Ward A, Graves J C, Omoniwa O F, Bashir N M, Maloney K, Emegbuonye L, et al. Comparison of seasonal malaria chemoprevention coverage in northern Nigeria via door-to-door, health facility and retail sector delivery. 2014;1):583-.

Ward 2015

Ward A V, Guillot A, Graves J C, Maloney K, Omoniwa O F, Emegbuonye L, et al. Impact of integrating the delivery of seasonal malaria chemoprevention with nutrition supplementation in northern Nigeria on health outcomes: A pragmatic intervention trial. 2015;93 (4 Supplement):250-.

Ward 2019

Ward A, Guillot A, Nepomnyashchiy L E, Graves J C, Maloney K, Omoniwa O F, et al. Seasonal malaria chemoprevention packaged with malnutrition prevention in northern Nigeria: A pragmatic trial (SMAMP study) with nested case-control. 2019;14(1):e0210692-.

Yerbanga 2016

Yerbanga R S, Yameogo B K, Yao F A, Ouattara S Y, Lefevre T, Da D, et al. Assessment of malaria transmission from human to mosquitoes in seasonal malaria chemoprevention in the western region of Burkina Faso. 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):520-1.

York 2017

York A. Seasonal malaria chemoprevention in the Sahel. 2017;17(6):588-.

Zongo 2016

Zongo I, Milligan P J, Tarning J, Nosten F, Ouedraogo J B. Dihydroartemisin-piperaquine for seasonal malaria chemoprevention. 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):400-.

Zongo 2017

Zongo I, Milligan P J, Tarning J, Nosten F, Ouedraogo J B, Institut de recherche en Science de la Santé Bobo-Dioulasso Burkina Faso. DIHYDROARTEMISIN-PIPERAQUINE FOR SEASONAL MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION. 2017;95:1pp.

Zongo 2019

Zongo I, Ouedraogo J B, Sawadogo Y, Lal S, Cairns M, Snell P, et al. Optimizing delivery of seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) for children under five years of age: Very high coverage consistently achieved through door-to-door campaigns in Burkina Faso. 2019;101 (5 Supplement):599-.

Zuilkowski 2014

Zuilkowski S S, Jukes M C. Early childhood malaria prevention and children's patterns of school leaving in the Gambia. 2014;84(Pt 3):483-501.

Additional references

1. World Malaria Report 2019. 2019, World Health Organization: Geneva.
2. Etard, J.F., et al., Childhood mortality and probable causes of death using verbal autopsy in Niakhar, Senegal, 1989-2000. *Int J Epidemiol*, 2004. 33(6): p. 1286-92.
3. Jaffar, S., et al., Changes in the pattern of infant and childhood mortality in upper river division, The Gambia, from 1989 to 1993. *Trop Med Int Health*, 1997. 2(1): p. 28-37.
4. Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention (SMC) for *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria control in highly seasonal transmission areas of the Sahel sub-region in Africa, in WHO Policy Recommendation. 2012, World Health Organization: Geneva.
5. Wilson, A.L. and I.P. Taskforce, A systematic review and meta-analysis of the efficacy and safety of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in children (IPTc). *PLoS One*, 2011. 6(2): p. e16976.
6. Meremikwu, M.M., S. Donegan, and E. Esu, Chemoprophylaxis and intermittent treatment for preventing malaria in children. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*, 2008(2): p. CD003756.
7. Sterne, J.A.C., et al., RoB 2: a revised tool for assessing risk of bias in randomised trials. *BMJ*, 2019. 366: p. l4898.
8. Higgins, J., Savovic, J., Page, M.J., Elbers, R.G, Sterne, J, Assessing risk of bias in a randomized trial, in *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions*, T.J. Higgins JPT, Chandler J, Cumpston M, Li T, Page MJ, Welch VA., Editor. 2019. p. 205-228.
9. Sterne, J.A., et al., ROBINS-I: a tool for assessing risk of bias in non-randomised studies of interventions. *BMJ*, 2016. 355: p. i4919.
10. Deeks JJ, J.H., Altman DG., Analysing data and undertaking meta-analyses., in *Cochrane handbook for systematic reviews of interventions.*, T.J. Higgins JPT, Chandler J, Cumpston M, Li T, Page MJ, Welch VA., Editor. 2019, The Cochrane Collaboration. p. 241-284.
11. Schünemann H, B.J., Guyatt G, Oxman A., Quality of evidence, in *GRADE handbook for grading quality of evidence and strength of recommendations.* , B.J. Schünemann H, Guyatt G, Oxman A., Editor. 2013, The GRADE Working Group, 2013.
12. ACCESS-SMC Partnership. Effectiveness of seasonal malaria chemoprevention at scale in west and central Africa: an observational study. *Lancet*. 2020 Dec 5;396(10265):1829-1840.

13. Cairns M, Ceesay SJ, Sagara I, Zongo I, Kessely H, Gamougam K, Diallo A, Ogboi JS, Moroso D, Van Hulle S, Eloike T, Snell P, Scott S, Merle C, Bojang K, Ouedraogo JB, Dicko A, Ndiaye JL, Milligan P. Effectiveness of seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) treatments when SMC is implemented at scale: Case-control studies in 5 countries. *PLoS Med.* 2021 Sep 8;18(9):e1003727.

14. Ndiaye, J. L. A.; Manga, I. A.; Tairou, F.; Ndiop, M.; Diallo, I.; Tine, R.; Ndiaye, M.; Faye, B.; Ndiaye, D.; Sarr, O.; Gaye, O.; Milligan, P. Impact of seasonal malaria chemoprevention after 3 years at scale in Southern Senegal *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene* November 2017;97 (5 Supplement 1):134.

15. Chandramohan D, Zongo I, Sagara I, Cairns M, Yerbanga RS, Diarra M, Nikièma F, Tapily A, Sompougou F, Issiaka D, Zoungrana C, Sanogo K, Haro A, Kaya M, Sienou AA, Traore S, Mahamar A, Thera I, Diarra K, Dolo A, Kuepfer I, Snell P, Milligan P, Ockenhouse C, Ofori-Anyinam O, Tinto H, Djimde A, Ouédraogo JB, Dicko A, Greenwood B. Seasonal Malaria Vaccination with or without Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention. *N Engl J Med.* 2021 Sep 9;385(11):1005-1017.

Reviews

Meremikwu 2005

Meremikwu M M, Omari A A, Garner P. Chemoprophylaxis and intermittent treatment for preventing malaria in children. 2005;(4):CD003756-.

Meremikwu 2008

Meremikwu M M, Donegan S, Esu E. Chemoprophylaxis and intermittent treatment for preventing malaria in children. 2008;(2):CD003756-.

Meremikwu 2012

Meremikwu M M, Donegan S, Sinclair D, Esu E, Oringanje C. Intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in children living in areas with seasonal transmission. 2012;(2):CD003756-.

Matangila 2015

Matangila J R, Mitashi P, Inocencio da Luz R A, Lutumba P T, Van Geertruyden J P. Efficacy and safety of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria in schoolchildren: a systematic review. 2015;14:450-.

Wilson 2011

Wilson A L, IPTc Taskforce. A systematic review and meta-analysis of the efficacy and safety of intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in children (IPTc). 2011;6(2):e16976-.